

June 11, 2018

cc: Virginia Steel, Norman and Armena Powell University Librarian

Dear Sharon Farb, Associate University Librarian for Special Collections and International Collaborations,

For the last decade, UCLA Library Special Collections (LSC) has relied heavily on a staff of temporary archivists. From 2009-2015, these temporary archivists were classified as staff positions (Principal Museum Scientists). Contracts ranged in length, sometimes as brief as four months, and were often renewed at the last minute, sometimes on the final day of the staff member's contract. In 2013, Temporary Librarian contract language was altered to be more specific about the conditions under which Temporary Librarian contracts were appropriate in an effort to close loopholes that allowed for UCLA to have over 20% of librarians in temporary appointments.¹ Following a labor-management meeting on the (mis)use of these classifications between UC-AFT and UC Office of the President, in January 2015 temporary Principal Museum Scientist positions were converted to Temporary Librarian positions, and temporary contracts were increased to two-year lengths.

These changes were intended to protect employees from being exploited by doing librarian-level work without providing them the status, compensation, title, or benefits commensurate with the Librarian series. Since then, however, the use of temporary archivists has increased. Within the last two years, ten temporary archivists have been employed in LSC. As of the writing of this letter, six temporary archivists are employed in LSC² (soon to be seven -- a new temporary archivist position is in the early stages of recruitment) and all of us are doing ongoing, i.e. not solely project-based or grant-funded, work. This is singularly egregious--other institutions typically have one or two project archivists who are hired on grant funded contracts. LSC is comprised of a staff of 31, which includes five curators (with two additional curatorial roles in the early stages of recruitment). In contrast, LSC's Collection Management unit is now comprised of a single supervisor³ and three permanent archivists, only one of whom is focused on processing collections. LSC cannot responsibly steward new acquisitions with that configuration, let alone its already large backlog, which is currently undiscoverable and inaccessible to the public. Simply put, it is unethical to continue collecting with the knowledge that there is no sustainable processing program in place. Furthermore, it places the UC Regents, the legal owners of material, at risk if a donor decides to claim that we are not following through on our commitment of responsible stewardship, as laid out in LSC's deed of gift.⁴

The practice of hiring archivists on temporary contracts negatively affects everyone involved -- the archivists, institutions, collections, donors, and users. As stated in OCLC's recent report *Research and Learning Agenda for Archives, Special, and Distinctive Collections in Research Libraries* (2017): "There is growing concern regarding ways in which insecure employment affects both the diversity of the profession and the cadre of early career professionals who often fill term roles, as well as how forced turnover, fluctuating staff resources, and the short-term frameworks inherent to project-based work affect our programs in the long term."⁵

The practice of hiring archivists on temporary contracts is problematic because:

- *It wastes UCLA Library's time and resources* -- Temporary contracts require that the Library recruit, hire, train, and onboard staff anew. With multiple meetings, interviews, phone calls, and writing assignments, the average commitment for members of the search committee is estimated to be between 40 and 80 hours for each recruitment,⁶ in addition to the time spent by other members of staff who meet with candidates multiple times. Temporary staff must apply for new positions mid-way through their contracts, further increasing turnover.

¹ See [Article 18, Temporary Appointees, Librarian \(Unit 17\) MOU, UC-AFT](#).

² UCLA Library currently employs a total of six temporary librarians -- all six are archivists in Library Special Collections.

³ With the recent departure of the Head of Collection Management, the only supervisory role remaining is the Head of Processing. Administration has not yet announced whether the Head of Collection Management position will be reposted.

⁴ See #8, 12, 13 in UCLA Library Special Collections Deed of Gift. (Form I - Revised July 2017).

⁵ Weber, Chela Scott. 2017. [Research and Learning Agenda for Archives, Special, and Distinctive Collections in Research Libraries](#). Dublin, OH: OCLC Research.

⁶ Megan Hahn Fraser "Job postings and search committees," 2017.

- *It wastes Library Special Collections' time and resources* -- Frequent recruiting, interviewing, onboarding, and training requires a significant investment of staff time. A staff that is continually in flux means that time that could otherwise be spent contributing to the strategic priorities of the department, Library, and campus must instead be spent onboarding and off-boarding staff.
- *It disrespects our donors, users, and collections, and subverts the mission of UCLA Library* -- LSC cannot properly make collections discoverable and safely provide access to materials by relying on an itinerant, and therefore less invested, archival workforce. This violates our agreements with donors, is irresponsible towards our users, and disrespects LSC's valuable research collections. As a result, LSC is thwarting UCLA Library's stated mission to "put users first" and "support open access to knowledge."⁷
- *It diminishes institutional knowledge* -- When their terms end, temporary librarians take away with them their knowledge of the systems, tools, and collections they have worked on. Losing this critical information weakens the department in the long-term because valuable skills, knowledge, and relationships disappear.
- *It inhibits long-term decision making* -- Not having a stable or predictable staff make-up prevents stability among LSC staff, which inhibits long term planning and policy setting, and prevents sustainability of programs and projects as well as the transfer of institutional knowledge.
- *It hinders professional development* -- The lack of job security for temporary librarians impacts their ability to develop professionally by not allowing them to be involved with long-term projects, give them the space to grow in a role, and at times not giving them the opportunity to go through an official review process (peer review).
- *It is financially harmful* -- Temporary librarians often do not have the opportunity to get raises, they have to move more often, and might experience periods of unemployment (exacerbated by the hiring process, which is still months-long for temporary positions). The precarity of temporary positions disproportionately affects people of color and places more barriers to entry into the profession. This directly negates the Library's avowed commitment to diversity of the library and the profession.
- *It damages archivists' personal lives* -- Job insecurity negatively affects one's ability to make major life decisions. They are more likely to move and have to start over. They will feel worried, anxious, and not in control of their futures. They have to spend leisure and vacation time identifying, applying to, and interviewing for jobs.
- *It undermines the professionalism, expertise, and worth of archivists* both in the UCLA Library and the field at large. Temporary archival positions as status quo sends the inaccurate message that archivists are disposable and that repeated short-term and fluctuating staffing can meet long-term institutional needs. This implicitly devalues our work and our status as professionals.

We, the temporary archivists, are involved with donor relations, classroom instruction, exhibitions, outreach and events, supervising graduate scholars, providing reference, creating documentation and policy, staff trainings, data migrations, systems implementation, and workflow changes. We are professionally involved at the campus, local, state, and national level. We are professionals with years of experience at top institutions. We went through competitive national searches (for some of us, multiple times). We are leaders in our field. We ask that the UCLA Library convert all six temporary archivists to potential career Librarian positions. By doing so, the UCLA Library will recognize the value archivists bring to our team, our collections, and our patrons. Additionally, we ask that the library discontinue the unfair, damaging, and inefficient practice of hiring librarians in temporary roles to perform core duties and functions, unless the position is tied directly to a source of outside funding.

Best,

Courtney Dean, Processing Archivist
 Lori Dedeyan, Processing Archivist
 M. Angel Diaz, Project Processing Archivist
 Melissa Haley, Processing Archivist
 Margaret Hughes, Collections Data Archivist
 Lauren McDaniel, Visual Materials Processing Archivist

⁷ [UCLA Library's mission statement.](#)

Support for UCLA Temporary Librarians

We, the undersigned, believe that the practice of hiring temporary librarians is harmful to all parties. We enthusiastically support the temporary librarians fighting for fairer and more sustainable hiring practices, and encourage UCLA Library Human Resources and the library administration to cease this practice and convert their positions to permanent.

Name	If UCLA: Department If non-UCLA: Title and Institution	Remarks (Optional)
Shira Peltzman	Library Special Collections	This is a harmful and short-sighted practice that negatively impacts both the department as well as the librarians involved.
Kelly Besser	Library Special Collections	
Charlie Chen	Digital Initiatives and Information Technology	
Louise Ratliff	Cataloging &c Metadata Center	This practice is disrespectful and unprofessional. It is a contract violation of the UC-AFT Unit 17 MOU, Article 18.
Cesar Reyes	Library Special Collections	
Jasmine Jones	Library Special Collections	
Claudia Horning	Cataloging & Metadata Center	
Annie Pho	Powell	
Miki Goral	Powell	We sought to correct this unfair practice in the last contract negotiations, but the University seems to be disregarding what was agreed to.
Santhosh David	DIIT	Temporary/Short term contracts helps none.
Michael Fehrf	Biomed	The Library's decision to engage in these unlawful actions is very disturbing.
Simon Lee	Powell	
Lauren Buisson	Library Special Collections	This practice undermines staff morale in ways that extends well beyond the temporary appointments. We come to trust and value our colleagues; these experiences enrich us all. When we lose our teammates those losses derail <u>all</u> of our work.
Teresa Barnett	Library Special Collections	The library needs to face the reality that archival processing is an on-going need, and we need to support it with career staff positions as we do any other Special Collections activity. It serves no one's interests to constantly be rehiring the same positions, and it is grossly unfair to the archivists who do the work.

Paul Priebe	Cataloging & Metadata Ctr.	
Jamie Jamison	Library Data Archive	
Caroline Miller	Cataloging & Metadata Center	
Matthew Vest	Music Library	
Courtney Hoffner	Science Libraries	The practice of hiring temporary archivists and librarians is unethical, demoralizing, and inefficient. I know first-hand, as a temporary librarian for many years, how harmful this practice is for our staff's personal and professional lives, and the disservice it does to the Library in terms of service, resources, and building institutional knowledge. We need to respect and support our wonderful, skilled colleagues by converting their positions to full-time permanent career positions.
Joseph Andrews	Cataloging & Metadata Center	
Tanya Akel	Anderson Library, former student	
Callie Holmes	Music Library	
Molly Haigh	Library Special Collections	
Tony Aponte	Science Libraries	
Dalena Hunter	Ralph J. Bunche Center for African American Studies Library and Media Center	
Melissa Beck	Law Library	This same issue arose when I was Chair-Elect of CAPA, in early 2013. A grievance was either filed or was about to be filed by the union about the misuse of temporary librarian positions for necessary, ongoing work. The UL at the time "settled" by converting the existing temporary positions into permanent ones. Why has this happened again in our library? Have we not learned anything? If there is work that is considered important, then provide the adequate long-term staffing for it.
Jessica Tai	UCLA Library Special Collections	
Alicia Reiley	Powell	
David Poepoe	YRL Access Service	
Marisa Méndez-Brady	YRL / Humanities & Social Sciences division of User Engagement	
Iris Garcia	Law Library	

Jane F Carpenter	Library Special Collections	
Martin Brennan	Scholarly Communication	I, like so many of my colleagues at UCLA, started in a temporary position. It was foolish and reckless for me to leave a tenure-track position at another institution to take on such a role, but I had personal motivation to make the move. How many qualified candidates decline to apply, or turn down a job offer, because of this? Library administration needs to show they are serious about recruiting the best candidates they can, and not looking to exploit early-career librarians who will accept insecure positions in a tough job market.
Leo Gonzalez	Preservation Program	
Nancy Norris	Cataloging & Metadata	
Stacy McKenna	Bibliographic Control Coordinator	In addition to the cost to the humans involved, the lack of continuity is a major blow to the collections involved. Consistency in processing and procedure improves discoverability of our collections and makes them a more valuable resource to the research community both here on campus and at large. The university is shooting itself in the foot by not making sure it's presenting the most accessible, consistently documented resources possible.
Nora Avetyan	Cataloging & Metadata Center	
Robert Gore	Arts Library	Where I previously worked, a decision was made to convert temporary librarian positions to full-time permanent positions. The effect on the library as whole was transformative. Our Dean, who had initially been opposed to the change, fully supported the initiative once she was able to see the full impact on the library and the College as a whole.
Nisha Mody	Science Libraries	I believe it is pertinent for the continuity, community, and overall respect of the profession for this temporary status be converted into full-time permanent positions. This will benefit the library as a whole to create collaborations, partnerships, and higher morale.
Bethany Myers	Biomedical Library	Committing to permanent LSC librarian and archivist positions will facilitate the processing and sharing of our collections, and will be a statement and example to other library units, the campus, and other institutions that we value the work of archival professionals.

Kelly Leong	Law Library	
Amanda Mack	Film & Television Archive	
Annette Doss	Film & Television Archive	
Peter Fletcher	Cataloging & Metadata Center	
T-Kay Sangwand	Digital Library Program	
David Cappoli	Law School Communications	
Rebecca Fenning Marschall	Clark Library	This use of temporary library staff positions negatively impacts the work of Library Special Collections as well as crucial interdepartmental relationships throughout the UCLA Library and affiliated units. Continually hiring temporary staff to fulfill core responsibilities is irresponsible and sends the very clear message that the UCLA Library does not value the work that our archivists perform -- and by extension, that we do not value the collections with which they work.
Andrew R. Perrine	SRLF	Past use of temporary staff positions throughout the Library, especially in Library Special Collections, has negatively impacted my own work in Imaging Services. I fully support the end of this practice.
Daniel Schoorl	Hispanic American Periodicals Index	
Philip Palmer	Clark Library	
Jeffrey King	Print Acquisitions	
Kevin Balster	Cataloging and Metadata Center	As someone who began in a temporary position that was primarily focused on ongoing, day-to-day operations, I can attest to the personal and professional insecurity that this situation causes. I had hoped that UCLA would have learned better than to accept the continuous loss of institutional knowledge, and the necessity to frequently train new staff, limiting the effectiveness and productivity of our library. I wholeheartedly support the ending of this practice across the board for positions that support day-to-day operations.
Neil Hodge	UAS-YRL	
Hannah Moshier	Library Preservation	
Judith Serlin		Member of the Public
Patrick Lavey	Law Library	These temporary positions hurt both the archivists and the UCLA Libraries. A permanent

		staff is crucial to the success of a great library.
Jane Collings	Library Special Collections	
Ann Bein	Cataloging - Retired	
Shahnaz Yousefnejadian	Cataloging & Metadata	
Julia Glassman	Powell Library	As someone who was originally hired as a temporary librarian to perform core duties in an essential line, I am surprised and dismayed that the UCLA Library continues this harmful and counterproductive practice.
Diana King	Arts Library	
Jennifer Chan	Scholarly Communication	
Lynda Tolly	Grace M. Hunt Memorial English Reading Room	If possible, moving these temporary appointments into potential career appointments would be a win/win.
Joanna Chen Cham	Powell Library	As someone who often encourages our undergraduates to utilize the incredible archival collections we have, I believe it is in the best interest of our students and researchers, the institution, and the library for these roles to be converted to permanent archivist positions in order to ensure that our resources can continue to be discovered and accessed. I have the utmost respect for my fellow colleagues who are doing this work.
Karly Wildenhaus	UCLA MLIS 2018; former student worker at the UCLA Arts Library	Reliance on temporary positions for staffing threatens the long-term sustainability of the very institutions who seek to steward and preserve our heritage for future generations. The precarity of these positions is also financially and emotionally harmful to those workers who continually demonstrate their dedication to Library Special Collections.
Caroline Cubé	Library Special Collections	<p>LSC is a living organism; we cannot expect to thrive if we keep lopping off our own arms and legs and ears.</p> <p>LSC staff all know that Simon Elliott, who processed A.Quincy Jones, is the Go-to guy for all things A.Quincy Jones. But who will be the Go-to guy for ArchivesSpace, or Barbara Morgan, or V Vale, or Collection X, Y, or Z if our archivists are not retained?</p> <p>To iterate what many have said, it can't feel good to know that you may not have a job two years after you went through a grueling interview process to get hired. Each month that</p>

		passes brings you closer to your end date. I love working here; I want the people with whom I work to feel secure and supported.
Michael Oppenheim	Rosenfeld Management Library	
Douglas E. Johnson	Chicano Studies Research Center	It is unconscionable that such a highly educated, well-trained, and dedicated group of professionals must live in a state of precarity.
Antonia Osuna-Garcia	Biomedical Library	
Doug Worsham	User Engagement / Science Libraries	I worked for years as a temporary lecturer and teacher and eventually had to leave teaching as a result of poor working and living conditions and continual job insecurity. Let's find a better solution for our staff.
Doug Daniels	DIIT	I've only ever been employed as a contract employee while at the Library. While I understand the circumstances around my hiring(s) may have necessitated this, I still think that every effort should be made to offer permanent positions whenever and wherever possible. It's not fun to have a timer ticking away at your gainful employment!
Jade Alburo	International Studies	
Aaron M. Bittel	Ethnomusicology Archive	As a professional archivist and librarian, I find the practice of abusing temporary positions deeply corrosive to the profession and to the committed professionals who dedicate themselves to it, analogous to the widespread abuse of temporary faculty positions in place of permanent ones. But as an archival educator I am even more troubled by this practice. The talented and hard-working students that I work with deserve to start their professional careers with the same opportunities for stable employment that all of us who have come before them have enjoyed. UCLA should be a better model among our peer institutions.
Kristian Allen	DIIT	
Kay Deeney	Biomedical Library	
Annie Watanabe-Rocco	YRL/LSC	
Xaviera S. Flores	Chicano Studies Research Center	
Russell A. Johnson	History & Special Collections for the Sciences, UCLA Library Special Collections	Having a corps of short-term temporary archivists is efficient for project-based work, but not for long-term programmatic planning and development of subject-related expertise and enthusiasm.

Rebecca Fordon	Law Library	
Rachel Green	Law Library	
Jennifer Lentz	Law Library	
Wil Lin	Library Preservation	
Stephanie Anayah	Law Library	
Peggy Alexander	Library Special Collections	
Joseph Orellana	DIIT	Even though I'm currently under a contract position and understand why that is so, I do not believe that this practice is sustainable, and that it is disrespectful, unprofessional and it contradicts our institutional value of building/instituting a strong culture.
Gabrielle Mittelbach	DIIT	This is a serious problem throughout the Library with various levels of staff.
Dawn Childress	DLP	
Noor Jabaieh	DIIT	
Zoe Borovsky	H&SS/YRL	Permanent positions are the best way for the library to developing and sustain deep, lasting relationships with students, faculty, and donors.
Simon Elliott	Library Special Collections	Special Collections used to have three full time, permanent manuscript processors. Their institutional knowledge alone contributed enormously to the service provided to readers, the quality of work produced, and the planning and development of the department. The hiring of temporary help to do everyday tasks does little to improve the working of the department.
Ruby Bell-Gam	International Studies	I agree with others that temporary, contract employment should not be used by a well established institution, such as UCLA, to fill essential, ongoing services and functions. I, too, had assumed that this issue was settled once for all several years ago, so I'm appalled to learn that there are still colleagues here with long-term temporary status. Just for the sake of fairness and organizational morale, such practices are not good for the Library or UCLA.
Cindy Kimmick	DIIT	I wholeheartedly concur with the letter and comments. In addition, I would like to mention the huge "soft cost" that DIIT-Ops has incurred in the last ten years, as our career staff numbers have dwindled. We are constantly in training mode because of the turnover in contract (and student) staff.

Peter Broadwell	DLP	
Jonathan Wilson	DIIT	It seems that hiring temporary staff does more harm than good, for the reasons outlined in this letter. Relying on them puts more stress on the remaining full time staff and results in a tremendous amount of institutional knowledge lost (or never gained), which is a detriment to the organization as a whole.
Yasmin Dessem	Library Preservation	There's an appropriate time and place for temporary/project based employment in this field and it can offer excellent opportunities, but the misapplication of these hiring practices does more harm than good to an organization. This letter undeniably indicates that a larger conversation about this issue needs to be addressed Library-wide. We all know that temporary hires handling ongoing work is an unfortunate reality in departments across the library, in all units, and perhaps even UC as a whole. By continuing this practice without critical evaluation of our ongoing responsibilities and greater transparency around the handling of permanent lines, we're not supporting and valuing our hires, our collections and our very real organizational needs. We risk losing valuable institutional knowledge and the ability to work together meaningfully for ongoing collaboration, innovation and growth which works against many of the guiding principles in our mission.
Allie Whalen	Library Preservation	
Bill Hackenberg	DIIT	As a contract worker I also support this initiative and stand with my fellow temps. While recognizing that budget constraints are real, it seems when temporary resources are continually renewed and/or replaced, the costs are about the same or higher when going with temps over the long term.
Shani Miller	Ethnomusicology Archive	
Amy Wong	Library Special Collections	
Josh Fiala	Library Special Collections	It is my understanding that temporary staff are not required to participate in activities that fall outside the scope of the terms of their appointment. That the Archivists felt a need to write this letter and garner support means that there should be a public conversation about appropriate permanent staffing across all functional areas of the Department.
Orchid Mazurkiewicz	Hispanic American Periodicals Index	

Chris Marino	Environmental Design Archives, Berkeley	
David Uhlich	UCSF Archives & Special Collections	
David Eifler	Environmental Design Librarian, UC Berkeley	
Sami Siegelbaum	Art	
Kelsi Evans	UCSF Archives and Special Collections	
Mackenzie Eason	Department of Political Science	
Thomas Winningham	Department of English	
Emily Vigor	Environmental Design Archives, Berkeley	This is a problem at UCLA and across UC campuses. The practice of hiring professional archivists in temporary positions seriously hinders our ability to grow in our careers, and to fully support and develop the work we do at these institutions. We cannot continue to rely on temporary positions to support our collections. Archivists, and our repositories, deserve better.
Noah Geraci	UC Riverside Library, Metadata and Technical Services	
Dana Cairns Watson	Continuing Lecturer in Writing Programs and Electrical and Computer Engineering	Temporary employment is bad for the library and bad for the employees--both the temporary librarians AND the faculty who work with librarians. The institutional knowledge of the librarians that I've worked with in the past, and the ongoing collaboration (related to teaching and also research) that I've been able to have with them, is too valuable to give up in exchange for the short-sighted gains to the university's budget. The University should be one institution that values and promotes increasing expertise.
Anna Yeakley	Bruin Resource Center	
Kathy Carbone	Department of Information Studies and CalArts Institute Archives	
Terri Anderson	Sociology	
Mia L. McIver, Ph.D.	Writing Programs President, UC-AFT	Temporary and contingent appointments harm our university community by introducing more uncertainty than necessary into archiving, librarianship, research, and teaching. If the work is ongoing, the jobs should be permanent.

Jean-Paul deGuzman	Asian American Studies & Interracial Dynamics GE Cluster	As a historian who has used Special Collections archives, and a faculty who sends students there for their own research, I am concerned about the treatment of these archivists. Such precarity does a disservice to the expertise of the temporary librarians and to the quality of the workplace and resources for students.
Elvia Arroyo-Ramirez	Special Collections & Archives, UC Irvine Libraries	This practice and its ramifications on staff morale and tension between professionalized and temporary staff is the reason why I have deterred from considering to apply for positions at LSC. I stand in full support of all LSC professionals on temporary positions. The professional community has benefited tremendously from their individual and collective contributions to the field. They deserve job security and opportunity for advancement that all library professionals in the UC system enjoy.
Lara Michels	Bancroft Library, UC Berkeley Head of Archival Processing	
Lindsay Wilhelm	Department of English	
Derek Christian Quezada	Special Collections & Archives, UC Irvine Libraries	I reiterate the statement of Elvia Arroyo-Ramirez and add further that I personally know these librarians and can attest to the tremendous impact and leadership they have shown in our profession. Security in their positions and financial recognition is due.
Kate Dundon	Supervisory Archivist UCSC Special Collections & Archives	
Amber West, Ph.D.	Lecturer, Writing Programs Assistant Director, Undergraduate Writing Center	UCLA's primary purpose as a public research university is the creation, dissemination, preservation and application of knowledge for the betterment of our global society. LSC's current hiring and staffing practices hamper this mission.
Paul Von Blum	Senior Lecturer, African American Studies and Communication	
Erica Fletcher	Anthropology	
Marjorie Bryer	Archivist, The Bancroft Library	
Lynn Boyden	Information Architect, USC ITS Web Services	You all already know where I stand on this issue. Hiring folks as temps to circumvent payment of benefits and securing employment is pretty underhanded.
Karl Lisovsky	Lecturer, UCLA Writing Programs,	Let's respect our archivists' expertise and talents and offer them what they deserve.

Michael Scott	Hispanic American Periodicals Index	
Teresa Mora	UC Santa Cruz Special Collections & Archives	
Audra Eagle Yun	UC Irvine Special Collections & Archives	
John Steinmetz	Lecturer, Herb Alpert School of Music	
Ruben Urbizagastegui	Distinguished Librarian, UCR	This is a harmful practice that negatively impacts both the department as well as the librarians involved.
Snowden Becker	MLIS Program Manager, Department of Information Studies	The UCLA Library has an opportunity to lead the field here by committing the necessary resources to the core functions of archival processing and management--as well as by retaining the talents of their outstanding staff.
Norma Corral	Retired Librarian, UC- AFT Local 1990 Treasurer	
David Gorshein	Lecturer, Dept. of Theater	
Christina Cicchetti	Librarian, UC Riverside	We relied on temporary librarians in my department for many years, so I can attest first-hand to how this practice contributes to low morale throughout the department, a loss of institutional knowledge, and the time wasted in the rehiring process.
Krystal Tribbett	UC Irvine Special Collections & Archives	
Melissa Dollman	UCLA Alumnae	Moving Image Archive Studies
Herbert U. Serrano	UCLA Extension, UCLA IS Alumni	The practice of hiring itinerant labor is detrimental to the institution, its stakeholders, and to the profession itself. The short-term economic gains are not worth the long term impact and only accelerate the practice of UC leadership seeing all labor as expendable.
Katherine Callen King	Professor Emerita, Comparative Literature and Classics, UCLA	Archival librarians are professionals who should be treated as such. Scholars who use archives and donors who contribute to archives should be treated with respect by ensuring that permanent librarians are the guardians of the archives.
Alix Norton	UC Santa Cruz Special Collections & Archives	
Sarah Jean Johnson	UCLA GSEIS Lecturer	

Anne J. Gilliland	Professor, UCLA Department of Information Studies	
Sarah T. Roberts	Assistant Professor, Department of Information Studies, UCLA	
Marissa Kings	Southern Regional Library Facility	
Judy Lee	Librarian, UC Riverside	How the Library treats its professionals is a reflection of the quality of its leadership. What message is the leadership sending to the scholars and donors who use the archives? How does this practice reflect upon the Library leadership and the institution?
Kristina Borrman	UCLA Art History PhD Student	
Andrew J Lau	Former Program Director for Instructional Content Development at UCLA Extension; UCLA IS Alum	
James Eason	Archivist for Pictorial Collections, The Bancroft Library, UC Berkeley	At Berkeley we face identical issues, relying heavily upon funded projects and temporary staff to accomplish them. We too are very concerned about the loss of expertise we continually suffer, and the drain of precious staff time on frequent recruitment of short-term professionals.
Jennifer Nelson	Librarian, the Robbins Collection, UC Berkeley School of Law	
Kiyoko Shiosaki	Instruction Services Librarian, Doe/Moffitt, UC Berkeley	
I-Wei Wang	Law Librarian, UC Berkeley	
Cristina Paul	UCLA Lab School, GSEIS	
Michelle Caswell	Department of Information Studies, GSEIS	
Jane Rosario	Librarian, Catalog & Metadata Services, UC Berkeley	
Marcia J. Bates	Professor Emerita, Department of Information Studies, UCLA	Several years ago I handed over 18 boxes of my professional papers to the University Archive for review. (These had been culled, over a marathon working week, from an original 80 linear feet of papers.) 98% OF THESE PAPERS WERE DISCARDED WITHOUT MY PERMISSION. The half-foot of papers retained were an incoherent and meaningless set. I not only never received an apology for discarding without my permission, I was told I should consider my publications to be my legacy instead. UCLA had no need for my papers, despite my being one of the most renowned researchers and consultants in the

		field over decades of technological change, and despite the fact that I chaired the Information Studies department for the two tumultuous years of the merger of GSLIS with GSEIS. Perhaps if there had been a more coherent permanent staff in the LSC, this travesty might not have occurred. I have since found another institution to take my remaining papers, and will certainly not leave money to UCLA.
Bergis Jules	UC Riverside Special Collections and University Archives	
D Ryan Lynch	UC Santa Barbara Library, Area Studies	
Margaret Phillips	Librarian, Social Sciences Division, UC Berkeley	
Helen Deutsch	Director, Center for 17th & 18th-C Studies/Clark Library	
Johanna Drucker	Distinguished Professor, Breslauer Professor of Information Studies	Work closely with Special Collections staff on projects and have contact with many students from IS who work there as well.
Jen Osorio	International Studies	
Gayatri Singh	Reference & Information Services Coordinator, and Librarian for Communication, UC San Diego Library	I held 3 temporary librarian positions in the UC system, and know first hand how hard it is when your career exists on short-term contracts. The UCs need to do better.
Claude Potts	Romance Languages Librarian, UC Berkeley	Having served on Committee on Appointment Promotion and Advancement (CAPA) for three years, I witnessed how a reliance on temporary librarians hurts not only the institution but also the chances of these second-tier librarians establishing themselves in the profession.
Julie Lefevre	Librarian, Institute of Governmental Studies, UC Berkeley	
Eric Milenkiewicz	Digital Initiatives Program Manager, UC Riverside Library	
Ariel Schudson	Independent Scholar, UCLA Alumna (MIAS program and Cinema and Media Studies)	I treasured the archival position that I held. But it was contractual. Many others have stated the basic issues that make contractual positions problematic- professional establishment, morale, etc. For me, this abbreviated term did not allow me to gain decent work experience or the confidence necessary to move forward to another workspace. Contract positions are incredibly damaging to this profession and to us as professionals.
Rachel Rosenfeld	Archivist at AMPAS, UCLA MLIS alum, former Bancroft Library UC	

	Berkeley contract employee	
Nina Mamikunian	Librarian for Literature and Theatre & Dance, UC San Diego Library	I loved my job at UCLA but I was a temporary librarian and I felt it difficult to set long term goals and pursue meaningful relationships with the faculty and students I served. Temporary employment is a cloud that hangs over all the work that you do.
Rebecca Townsend	UCLA MLIS alum, former UCLA Library student employee (YRL, Powell, LSC)	
Raphael Sasayama	UCLA MLIS, Stacks manager, Balch Art Research Library, LACMA	The goal is clear, so make it work!
Alison Lipman	Lecturer, EEB Dept.	I understand how difficult it is to dedicate yourself fully to a job when it is only temporary. I have this same problem as a lecturer with year to year contracts. UCLA needs to move past this problem by hiring outstanding staff/faculty on a permanent basis. Hiring temporary staff undermines the work done by the university and is ultimately bad for students.
Laurel McPhee	Supervisory Archivist (Special Collections & Archives, UC San Diego Library)	UCLA's LSC hiring practices for archival work are unethical, untenable, and ultimately unsustainable. Sound stewardship of thousands of feet of records and personal papers requires full-time, permanent staff.
Andrew Wallace	Digital Library Development	<p>At UCLA I've been working on various machine learning projects using our collections, which have the potential to produce innovative results that would reflect very well on the library. I've sensed a lot of interest from the administration in this kind of work.</p> <p>Unfortunately, I'm not sure the administration understands the degree to which this work builds on a foundation of basic librarianship. For all the high-tech appeal of machine learning, it fundamentally depends on good data, and our librarians are the ones who produce that data. We have excellent archivists but they are overworked and turnover is too high. The library's failure to invest in the people doing that work has stymied our ability to do the cutting-edge work we would like to do.</p> <p>Finally, as a contract employee myself I am very aware I could make a lot more money in the tech industry. I am committed to UCLA's public mission but find it hard to justify the lower salary in the absence of long-term security and when the library is unwilling to invest in the</p>

		librarians who enable the technological work I'd like to be doing.
Michael Meranze	Professor of History	
Megan Hahn Fraser	Marcus A. McCorison Librarian, American Antiquarian Society. Former Co-Head of Collection Management at UCLA Library Special Collections.	
Corliss Lee	Instruction Services Division, UC Berkeley Library	
Ariel Deardorff	Data Services Librarian, UCSF Library	
Janine Henri	UCLA Arts Library	It is one thing to hire temporary archivists to work on grant-funded projects that have a specific end date. But hiring temporary archivists for ongoing, core, day-to-day operations of the department does sound like a violation of the UC-AFT Unit 17 MOU, Article 18 contract. I concur that this practice is also disrespectful and unprofessional.
Irene Gates	Robert S. Peabody Institute of Archaeology, Temporary Archivist	
Yajun Mo	Assistant Professor, History Department, Boston College; UCSC alum	
Eric Hounshell	Lecturer, UCLA Department of History, PhD UCLA 2017	Graduate training and research at UCLA in history and neighboring fields depend on the expertise, institutional knowledge, and professional training of "temporary" librarians at LSC and the unique CFPRT program. I have called upon the faculty and graduate students of my department to support this open letter.
Jessica Pigza	Outreach and Exhibits Librarian, Special Collections & Archives, UC Santa Cruz	
Muriel C. McClendon	Associate Professor, History	
Aaron Samuels	PhD program, NELC, Jewish History	
Roi Ball	PhD Candidate, UCLA History	
Chris Bingley	History Department	
Jennifer Manoukian	PhD student, UCLA NELC, Armenian Studies	
Daniel Ohanian	PhD Student in History	

Vipin Krishna	PhD Student in History	
Hannah Mandel	Archivist, Center for Curatorial Studies at Bard College, UCLA MLIS	
Sarah Walsh	PhD Candidate, UCLA History	
Madina Thiam	PhD Candidate, UCLA History	
Javier Munoz	PhD Student, UCLA History	
Liana Katz	MURP '18, UCLA Luskin School of Public Affairs	
Michael Dean	PhD Student, UCLA History	
Tania Bride	PhD Candidate, UCLA History	
Chris Mott	SCL, UCLA English	Echoing and amplifying comments from Cham, Borovsky, Watson, McIver, deGuzman, Drucker, Wallace, and Hounshell, I'm signing because this practice impairs UCLA's educational mission. I know many English Department TAs who incorporate Special Collections projects into their curriculum--and important and growing trend across the nation--and the students as well as the teachers benefit from the consistency and coherence of institutional and professional knowledge of librarians given the chance to develop that knowledge.
Deborah Aschheim	Art	member of public who uses UCLA research resources, former lecturer in Dept of Art at UCLA
Lisa Monhoff	Project Archivist, The Bancroft Library	
Susan Powell	GIS & Map Librarian, UC Berkeley	
Nana Osei-Opare	PhD Candidate, UCLA History	
Claire Lavagnino	UCLA PhD 2013, Lecturer, Department of Italian	
Sarah McClung	Collection Development Librarian, UCSF	
Miriam Posner	Assistant Professor, Information Studies	I love collaborating with our librarians at UCLA! However, my ability to do so is really hindered when workers are casualized. I can't count on them to be there when I need them, and to have the institutional memory necessary to navigate the library and administration at UCLA. I know my friends in Special Collections are working so hard, and I really want to see their work compensated by fair and stable

		employment terms.
Charlie Macquarie	Digital Archivist, UCSF Library Archives & Special Collections	My colleagues at UCLA Library Special Collections are some of the hardest working and smartest archivists I know, and they deserve to have their labor honored by acknowledging the necessity of their positions. This persistent problem at (many) UC Archival Repositories needs to be acknowledged and addressed.
Erin Hurley	CAVPP/California Revealed, UCLA MLIS	As a fellow archivist, I have experienced firsthand how damaging this practice can be, and I hope to see archivists treated with the respect they deserve.
Rachel Mandell	Metadata Librarian, USC	In solidarity I sign this letter to acknowledge the labor of my colleagues and to recognize the impact they have on the university and the greater library profession. This harmful practice is inefficient and unsustainable-- it needs to stop.
Bolton Doub	Archival Projects Librarian, USC Libraries Special Collections	I am currently working on my third contract-based two-year archives processing project in a row. These temporary hiring practices in the archives profession are not sustainable for any party involved.
Mark Simon Haydn	Project Archivist, NYU Libraries	I am signing this in support of the archivists' efforts to do their work with stability and dignity. The arguments made about the ill-effects of short-term employment on collection care are strong and true, but UCLA should not require additional persuasion or metrics to give their employees meaningful and dignified working lives.
Ashley Blewer	Independent	
Stacy Wood	Assistant Professor, University of Pittsburgh School of Computing and Information - UCLA MLIS, PhD	
Roderic Crooks	Assistant Professor, Department of Informatics, UC Irvine	UCLA Libraries cannot build "a library of the future" without equity for the information professionals who execute the core mission of the institution.
Seth Erickson	Penn State Libraries CLIR Postdoctoral Fellow	
Dorothy Berry	Digital Collections Program Manager, Houghton Library - Harvard University Libraries	The practice of depending on contingent labor is both unfair to workers and disruptive to the field as a whole.
Alexis A. Antracoli	Assistant University Archivist for Technical Services, Princeton	

	University Library	
Elizabeth Skene	Assistant Professor, Special and Digital Collections Librarian, Western Carolina University	
Mallory Furnier	Archivist, Urban Archives and Old China Hands Archives, California State University, Northridge	Prior to my current position I was a project hopping temporary archivist for seven years in the same institution. Temporary labor is not a substitute for permanent staff, and serves as a unsustainable band-aid for operational needs. Our profession's labor practices need to change and UCLA has an opportunity to set the tone as a leading institution.
Kelly Bolding	Project Archivist for Americana Manuscript Collections, Princeton University Library	
Morten Bay	Ph.D. Candidate, Dept. Of Information Studies, UCLA	
David A. Wallace	Clinical Associate Professor, School of Information, University of Michigan	
Lauren Sorensen	PhD student, UCLA Information Studies; Association of Moving Image Archivists' Secretary & Director of the Board	
Yvonne M. Eadon	PhD Student, UCLA Information Studies, former CFPRT Scholar at UCLA LSC	
Carlin Soos	PhD Student, UCLA Department of Information Studies; recently hired CFPRT Scholar at UCLA LSC	I have had amazing experiences collaborating with the librarians and archivists working throughout UCLA's library system. Their familiarity with their collections and passion for helping students and researchers is a beautiful and needed asset to the UCLA community. All of these individuals deserve the utmost respect and support from the University, its members, and the academic community. This lack of stability is unsustainable for our institution and insulting to the important contributions gifted by these talented professionals.
April Feldman	University Archivist, California State University, Northridge	
Kelly Kress	Assistant Archivist Los Angeles Philharmonic Association, Former Processing Archivist at UCLA Library Special Collections	Signing in solidarity with my former UCLA colleagues. This unsustainable and demoralizing practice needs to end. It would be wonderful and also very appropriate to see the efforts of the archivists who wrote this letter realized

		now, to benefit future archivist work at UCLA and everywhere.
Gracen Brilmyer	PhD student, UCLA Department of Information Studies	
Julieta Garcia	Archivist, International Guitar Research Archives (IGRA), CSU, Northridge	I was in a grant funded temporary position for a long time. I didn't know if I would have a job when my contract would end. Luckily now I am in a stable position and feel like I am part of the institution.
Karl-Rainer Blumenthal	Web Archivist, Internet Archive	
Joseph Gallucci	Project Archivist, Los Angeles Philharmonic Association	
Dinah Handel	Digitization Services Manager, Stanford University	Temporary positions negatively impact archives at all levels, as well as the field at large. I sign in solidarity with my colleagues at UCLA. As someone with a 3 year term position, I share similar frustrations.
Athena Christa Holbrook	Collection Specialist, MoMA	
Brendan Coates	Sr. Archivist, Oral History Projects, AMPAS	
Celeste Brewer	Processing Archivist, Columbia University Rare Book and Manuscript Library	Every time a temporary staff member leaves a position, valuable institutional knowledge is lost.
Ethan Gates	Independent	
Brian E. Davis	Digital Production & Digital Preservation Supervisor, Oregon State University Libraries & Press	
Tricia Patterson	Digital Preservation Analyst, Harvard Library	
Alyssa V. Loera	Head of Digital Services and Technology, Cal Poly Pomona University Library	
David Staniunas	Archivist, Presbyterian Historical Society	
Nicole Contaxis	Project Coordinator, NYU Health Sciences Library	
Andrew Weaver	Digital Infrastructure and Preservation Librarian, Washington State University Libraries	
Marie Lascu	Audiovisual Archivist, Crowing	

	Rooster Arts + Digital Archivist, Ballet Tech + XFR Collective, New York, NY	
Seth Anderson	Software Preservation Program Manager, Yale University Library	As a former temporary staff member, I know first hand the challenges and undue burden this practice imposes on individuals who devote themselves to the institutions who gladly take advantage. I hope to see this practice come to an end and sign in support of my colleagues at UCLA.
Vicky Steeves	Librarian for Research Data Management and Reproducibility, New York University	Signing in solidarity with my UC colleagues, and with all my colleagues suffering under these stressful conditions.
Katie Mika	Data Services Librarian, University of Colorado Boulder	
Eddy Colloton	Assistant Conservator, Denver Art Museum	I will be leaving my 2nd temporary position in a row to start yet another temporary position soon (after receiving an MA degree in 2016). I have had to leave each of my previous positions before my projects were completed in order to assure that I could maintain employment (and therefore financial security). This has lead to projects remaining incomplete after I was forced to leave early. Temporary positions harm the institutions that create them, just as they are a burden for those that fill the positions. The UCLA libraries, and their librarians, will be better served by full time, permanent hires.
Pamela Vadakan	Associate Director, California Revealed, California State Library	UCLA Libraries could lead the way for all UC Libraries, and the library/archives/museum field in general, which depend too much on grant-funded, temporary, staff for long-term collections care. I wholeheartedly support the effort of librarians and archivists at UCLA, and UC-AFT, to change the system. Collections, and the professionals that take care of these collections, deserve the investment.
Tim Walsh	Fellow, Library Innovation Lab at Harvard University	
Rebecca Ruud	Media Archivist, Paramount Pictures Archives; UCLA Alumnae and former Clark Library student worker	The use of temporary librarians and archivists, especially in the special collections is harmful to our profession and institutions. The most important quality for an employee in these institutions is knowledge of their collections. Without the ability to complete processing large collections, and the ability to gain familiarity with collections, we cannot adequately provide patrons with relevant materials.
Jennifer Bolmarcich	Bicentennial Project Archivist,	As a new professional and a current project

	Amherst College	archivist, I am sorry to see such reliance on misclassification and mistreatment of archivists and librarians at UCLA. This is a profession-wide problem, and to see this institution--one charged with educating new archivists and librarians--abnegate the responsibilities of professional mentoring and stewardship is disheartening. I support the librarians and archivists at UCLA who are working with their colleagues in UC-AFT, to correct these exploitative practices.
Jessica Storm	Media Archivist, Paramount Pictures; UCLA Alum; former contract archivist, UCLA Film and TV Archive	Being moved from one contract position to another at UCLA and elsewhere over a number of years, I have seen firsthand how professionals can be exploited for institutional or corporate gain. It is unfair and undermines the reputability that we were taught to maintain while in grad school and throughout our careers.
Caitlin Denny	Media Archivist, Paramount Pictures Archives; UCLA Alumnae and former UCLA LSC CFPRT scholar	The practice of hiring temporary LIS employees in the UCLA LSC is dishonorable and act of malice. Requiring an MLIS for a position that is planned to be exterminated is a blow to the professionalism of LIS workers nationwide. We are deserving of the same securities, benefits and wages as other permanent positions in the UC system. The LIS community is motivated and ready to fight this injustice.
Alejandra Espasande	Coordinator, Academy Preservation and Foundation Programs; UCLA Alumnae	At times people are pushed out of the profession because of this very reason, openings for temporary positions and lack of permanent jobs. It is not good for the morale of a trained professional to be confronted with such lack of opportunities and treatment from part of prestigious institutions.
Erica Titkemeyer	AV Conservator & Project Director, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill;	
Rebecca Bucher Wollner	Assistant Librarian, Design Institute of San Diego; former LSC library/student assistant	
Joyce Gabiola	PhD Student, UCLA Department of Information Studies	
Tammi Kim	Special Collections and Archives Technical Services Librarian, University of Nevada, Las Vegas; UCLA Alumnae	
Mark Edward Heuck	Film historian, freelance researcher	
Amanda Cheung	UCLA MLIS alum, former Student	

	Assistant & CFPRT at UCLA LSC	
Patricia Garcia	UM Assistant Professor	
Nicholas Beyelia	Librarian, Los Angeles Public Library	This is incredibly disrespectful to accredited professionals and needs to stop.
Karla Irwin	Special Collections and Archives Technical Services Librarian, University of Nevada, Las Vegas	
Ashley Chase	Project Archivist, Bernard Becker Medical Library, Washington University School of Medicine. UCLA alumnae	
Sara Seltzer	Institutional Archivist, J. Paul Getty Trust; UCLA MLIS alum	
Teresa Soleau	Digital Preservation Manager, J. Paul Getty Trust, UCLA MLIS alum	I worked for many years in temporary positions doing core work (including digital preservation!) and I have managed departments with temporary positions. I agree with all the reasons outlined above - particularly the waste of time in dealing with staff turn-over and the loss of institutional knowledge.
Summer Espinoza	Digital Archivist, California State University, Dominguez Hills sespinoza@csudh.edu	Temporary positions are rarely justifiable for the level of expertise and longevity needed for even project positions. How can temporary positions fulfill the archival mission of maintaining long-lasting records? It is ineffective and inefficient in the long run. I agree that is is a great opportunity for setting a trend for change.
Sean Savage	Academy Film Archive	
Mary Haberle	Web Archivist, Internet Archive	
Brendan Lucas	UCLA Alum; Outfest UCLA Legacy Project	Solidarity, not precarity.
Joe Carrano	Digital Archivist, MIT Libraries	
Elizabeth England	Digital Archivist, Johns Hopkins University Sheridan Libraries	
Samantha DeWitt	Resource sharing specialist, Harvard Libraries	Replacing long-term library and archives positions with temporary staff is both unethical and short-sighted. Continually having to train new hires significantly reduces a department's efficiency and cohesion.
Rebecca Fraimow	Digital Archives Manager, WGBH	Signing in solidarity! Basing an institution's sustainability around temporary staff hires (when the university is fully capable of hiring permanent staff) is not only unethical, but poor

		preservation planning
Jennie Freeburg	Librarian/Archivist	This practice is harmful to the profession as a whole, and we should all examine the ways in which we perpetuate it. Solidarity.
Andrew Berger	Senior Digital Archivist, Computer History Museum	I began my career as an archivist in a temporary, term-limited position at an academic library (not UCLA). Everything in this letter rings true to my experience at that library, and to the experiences of the many other archivists and librarians I've spoken to about temporary positions.
Tanya Goldman	Phd Candidate, NYU	Archivists are bedrocks of institutional memory and an invaluable tool for scholars to produce knowledge. Scholars cannot produce work without their expertise. These should be full-time positions. Universities must find resources to support the invaluable services they provide.
Timothy E Wilson	Film & Television Archive	Employee turnover is wasteful on so many levels. Most importantly, it's time to invest in human beings, and give them the respect and job security they deserve, and whose return on investment is priceless.
Dan Erdman	Media Burn Archive	
Beaudry Allen	Archival Processing Specialist & Digital Productions Coordinator, UC Santa Barbara	
Robert D. Montoya	Assistant Professor, Information and Library Science, Indiana University Bloomington. Former Head of Public Services, UCLA Library Special Collections.	
Alena McNamara	Librarian, Tower Hill Botanic Garden	
Susan Kriete	Librarian II, Milstein Division, NYPL	Institutions that have enough funds to acquire collections must also budget enough funds for permanent staff to properly care for them and make them accessible to the public
Tanya Zanish-Belcher	Director, SCA, Wake Forest University	
Alison Clemens	Assistant Head of Arrangement & Description, Yale University Library	
Alice Sara Prael	Digital Archivist, Beinecke Rare Book & Manuscript Library	
Stephanie Bennett	Collections Archivist, SCA, Wake	The damages of temporary jobs are

	Forest University	well-described above. I certainly make note of institutions that rely on temporary labor; how could I make a career for myself at such an institution?
Rachel Ward	Recent recipient of the National Digital Stewardship Residency (NDSR) fellowship	
Desiree Goodwin	Harvard Library Resource Sharing	This is an attack on labor rights, the library profession, and the sustainability of scholarship and communities.
Addie Owens	Harvard Library Resource Sharing	
Kathryn Gronsbell	Digital Collections Manager, Carnegie Hall	
Jade Finlinson	UCLA MLIS, former library assistant at LSC	
Joshua Zimmerman	Archivist/Records Manager, Archdiocese of Seattle	
Zack Lischer-Katz	University of Oklahoma, CLIR Postdoc in Data Curation	
Penelope Neder-Muro	Processing Archivist, California Institute of Technology	
Stella Castillo	Project Archivist, Cal State Dominguez Hills	
Christine Rank	Manager of Information, The Wendt Museum, UCLA MLIS alum	
Amanda Roth	Instructional Technologies Librarian, UC San Diego	As a former temporary appointment, that was made permanent, it is possible to hire full time positions economically.
Brooke Ramos	UCLA '08; Librarian, Clovis Community College, CA	Temporary positions, as with any position, are expensive to recruit and hire for and in addition, when the position ends you lose the investment in that person and their invaluable institutional knowledge and memory. The program will not reach its full potential if you continue on with staffing the archives with a temporary staff and this practice devalues the archivists who have put in many years of hard work and dedication to their profession and into UCLA itself.
Jillian Cuellar	Director of Special Collections at Tulane University; former Head of Collection Management at UCLA Library Special Collections	Successful special collections programs cannot rely on project staff for sustainability, growth, and innovation. To do so is short-sighted, and unfair to the project staff, the permanent staff, and the users who donate and use our collections and support our work. While project

		positions can be mutually beneficial when used appropriately, they should not be a permanent solution to ongoing operational needs. LSC has benefited enormously from the skills, intelligence, and ambition of its project staff. If they cannot be offered permanent positions, then the Library should make a commitment to implementing new approaches to collection stewardship that do not contribute to the instability of the special collections labor force. Recalibrating collecting efforts to match the capacity of permanent resources would be a good place to start.
Jennifer Kishi	Archivist, Sterling Ruby Studio	
Brenda Flora	Archivist, Amistad Research Center	In addition to all the reasons outlined here, temporary employment is also harmful to the institution because it robs it of institutional knowledge and the ability to build and maintain lasting relationships with donors and patrons, which is vitally important particularly in archives.
Laura Cherry	Image Coordinator, Los Angeles County Museum of Art	
Andrea Hoff	Archives Specialist, Santa Clara University	In solidarity.
Shelley Carr	Resource Sharing, University of San Francisco	Students pay for the privilege of services by respected and skilled archivists and other library staff, by only filling these important positions with temporary workers, it reflects poorly on the institution of UCLA, and shows that they believe that disrespected workers are good enough for this work. By exploiting these archivists, they devalue the respected status of the University and disprove any stated interest in fairness, equality, and respect.
Mary Stark	Librarian II, Beverly Hills Public Library, Fine Arts Librarian	
Mario H. Ramirez	CLIR Postdoctoral Fellow, Indiana University, Bloomington	As a former Project Archivist at two different institutions, I can personally attest to the economic and personal precarity that I experienced as a product of my temporary status. Moreover, the impact this had on the trajectory of my career has been immeasurable, and continues to have ramifications for me today.
Sonya Rao	PhD Candidate, Anthropology, UCLA	
L. Chizu Morihara	Librarian, UC Santa Barbara Library	

Kristin Lipska	Digital and Media Archives Coordinator, San Francisco Symphony	
Jim Van Buskirk	Librarian II (retired), San Francisco Public Library	
Mari Khasmanyman	Archival Processing Specialist for the California Ethnic and Multicultural Archives (CEMA), Special Research Collections, UC Santa Barbara Library	There needs to be a UC wide consistency of ranking of the archival profession. Pay and class should be equal to librarian employee status. Collections aren't temporary and backlog is inevitable. Temp positions result in newer employees processing supplemental materials with little institutional knowledge available.
Cristela Garcia-Spitz	Digital Initiatives Librarian, UC San Diego Library	I started in a temporary position at UC San Diego Library, and I can attest to the struggle to try and maintain your job responsibilities and plan for projects and activities that are on a 5-year timeline, when your employment at the institution is only for a 2-year contract. It's unrealistic and unhelpful to all those involved - faculty and students, as well as Library colleagues, who relying on the work.
John Carl Stucky	Library Director, C. Laan Chun Library, Asian Art Museum, San Francisco	
Daisy Muralles	Information and Reference Specialist, UCSB Library Special Research Collections	
Sandy Rodriguez	Head of Digital Archives & Stewardship, University of Missouri--Kansas City	This practice harms library workers, the institution, and the communities we serve.
Eira Tansey	University of Cincinnati	Over-reliance on temporary labor undermines the larger mission of cultural heritage and documentary memory.
Sarah Hamerman	Princeton University Library	Relying on temporary staff -- especially when those professionals are refused a comparable salary, benefit package, and opportunities for professional growth with their permanent-staff peers -- devalues the library and archival profession as a whole. How can we care for our collections if we don't care for the people who maintain them?
Samantha Winn	Collections Archivist, Virginia Tech	I urge UCLA and all other large universities relying on temporary labor to immediately stop this unconscionable, shameful, and deeply unsustainable practice. It exploits the good will and livelihood of archival professionals and undermines our service to patrons, donors, and colleagues. Cheers to the authors of this letter

		for clearly articulating one of the most pernicious labor abuses in LIS.
Kira Dietz	Acquisitions & Processing Archivist, Virginia Tech	
Krystal Boehlert	Visual Resources Specialist, UC Riverside	
Jeremy Brett	Cushing Memorial Library & Archives, Texas A&M University	Temporary labor is an unfair crutch that does not benefit institutions or the people who staff them.
Akunna Eneh	Programs & Community Outreach Librarian, Boston Public Library	
Anthony Wright de Hernandez	Community Collections Archivist, Virginia Tech	As was well explained in this letter, temporary positions negatively affect workers, the institution, and the work. Long-term planning is precluded when all workers are temporary workers. When every position posted by an institution is temporary, it also gains that institution a negative reputation within the profession. I recently completed a job search where I specifically excluded institutions like UCLA as potential employers because of this practice. I'm sure others have done the same.
Anna Clutterbuck-Cook	Reference Librarian, Massachusetts Historical Society	As a reference librarian in a special collections environment, I am keenly aware of the institutional memory and expertise that is lost with each staff member hired away. While temporary positions have their place in the library workplace, they should never become a permanent solution to staffing. The institution, as well as the workers who hold those positions, suffer as a result.
Ruth Kitchin Tillman	Cataloging Systems and Linked Data Strategist (Assistant Librarian), Penn State University Libraries	This letter aptly describes how reliance on temporary positions for work beyond special projects both injures the precarious workers who hold them and damages the work, culture, climate, continuity, and effectiveness of such departments overall. I join them in asking UCLA to commit to its regents and donors by committing to the workers who steward their collections.
Mark A. Matienzo	Collaboration and Interoperability Architect, Stanford University Libraries	
Lindsey Benjamin	Archives Specialist, Oregon Historical Society	This letter speaks to the pervasive and damaging nature of temporary positions in our field of employment. As institutions working to preserve and share information with communities, we need to value and support

		those working towards these important tasks via expertise gained through years of hard work and commitment.
Carmen Mitchell	Scholarly Communication Librarian, Cal State San Marcos	
Elena Colón-Marrero	Digital Processing Archivist, Computer History Museum	
Jessica E. Johnson	Processing Archivist, Virginia Commonwealth University Libraries	
Libby Coyner	Archivist, Elon University	
Laura Bang	Distinctive Collections Librarian/Archivist, Villanova University	Over the past several years, I have watched with alarm the growing number of temporary/contract positions within our field. This practice devalues the profession and harms both the individuals and the institutions. If staff are not working on a temporary project, they should not be temporary staff.
Tim Lentz	Library Director, Midland University	
Dennis Doros	Co-owner of Milestone Films	
Amy Wickner	Electronic Records Archivist, University of Maryland Libraries	The practices and experiences this letter describes are systematic across libraries and archives. I support my colleagues in speaking up for change and encourage fellow archivists and librarians with job security to use any and all influence we can for same.
Matt Stahl	University Archivist, University of California, Santa Barbara	Temporary positions are detrimental to our profession on the whole.
Jennifer Johnson	Senior Archivist, Cargill, Incorporated	
Noah Huffman	Archivist for Metadata, Systems, and Digital Records, Duke University	
Stacey Erdman	Digital Archivist, Beloit College and Instructor for the Digital POWRR Project	I stand in solidarity with my colleagues, and echo all the sentiments contained in this missive. My professional career also began in a temporary position. It impacted all personal and professional decisions in my life, because I had absolutely no feelings of security, and I continually felt devalued as a professional. Libraries need to take a stand and put an end to precarious hiring practices.
Abbey Thompson	Assistant Library Director, AMDA Los Angeles	The over-use of temporary/contract positions and the reclassification of professional librarian positions to the paraprofessional-sphere have become an epidemic in libraries. It is destructive

		to the workforce and devalues us as a profession.
Matt Ruen	scholarly communication librarian, Grand Valley State University, MI	Signing in support, solidarity, and total admiration of the authors of this letter. The courage and integrity required to share this letter are qualities that any library should seek in employees, and which could only enrich UCLA's mission and reputation.
Linda Kobashigawa	Librarian, Fresno City College	As a UCLA alumnus and former library employee of the UCLA Libraries I am disappointed that the practice of hiring and stringing along temporary librarians and archivists has continued. There must be a better way to treat employees who deliver valuable services and scholarship for their institution.
Michele Jennings	Art Librarian, Ohio University	Precarious work in libraries and archives is bad for institutions, bad for collections, bad for patrons, and bad for the profession. Period. (UC alumni, UCSC 2012)
Alexandra Krensky	Processing Archivist, University of Wisconsin-Madison	
Jennifer V. Mitchell	Head of Archival Processing, LSU Libraries Special Collections	
Courtney Blossom	YA Librarian NYPL, Contract Librarian Belcan Engineering	As a contract librarian, I know that the work that I perform, offsite and onsite, is NECESSARY to the performance of my engineers. It cannot be undervalued. When you remove the information professionals, you risk all future work your institution could be possible of creating.
Jennifer Whitlock	Archivist, Vignelli Center for Design Studies, Rochester Institute of Technology	
Shannon O'Neill	UCLA MLIS alum, former YRL student worker, and Director of Barnard Archives and Special Collection	
Kellee E. Warren	Instructor and Special Collections Librarian, University of Illinois at Chicago	Temporary positions and contracts create an atmosphere of poor service. When you don't allow professionals the time to learn the collections, and serve students, faculty, and community members, this reflects poorly on the university.
Lindsay (Hansen) Brown	CSUN, formerly UCLA Music Library	I was fortunate to be a temporary librarian for only a year and transition to a full-time, tenure-track position. Too many librarians are

		undervalued, underpaid, and get stuck in a loop of temporary contracts.
Rose L. Chou	Budget & Personnel Manager, American University Library	
Kurt Hanselman	Metadata Specialist, UC San Diego Library; UCLA MLIS alum.	
Hillel Arnold	Assistant Director, Head of Digital Programs, Rockefeller Archive Center	
Jaena Rae Cabrera	Librarian I, San Francisco Public Library	
Alexandra Chassanoff	Research Program Officer, Educopia Institute	
Jennifer Pierre	Department of Information Studies, uUCLA WI+RE	I am constantly inspired by the passion, dedication, creativity, and expertise of the archivists and librarians I have had the pleasure of working with, despite many of them facing distressing financial and career instability from the precarity of their positions. I agree wholeheartedly that expecting them to continue this caliber of work and invest in long-term developments while assigning them to temporary positions is unsustainable, short-sighted, and a severe detriment to the profession and to the campus as a whole. I encourage the UCLA LSC to take this opportunity to reverse the troubling trend across libraries, academic departments, and universities more broadly of devaluing this work through the continued removal of permanent positions.
Ebony Magnus	Assessment & User Experience Librarian, Southern Alberta Institute of Technology	
Xiaoda Wang	Former project archives assistant at Getty Research Institute. Former project archivist at Huntington Library	Project archival work is toxic for all involved. Project archivists make long-term plans for historical and institutional assets, yet they have been forced to sacrifice their own long-term plans. It's a guarantee any department with project archivists will lose team morale and respect for leadership.
Penny Scott	Librarian, University of San Francisco	
Angie Lyons	Librarian, West Coast University, Los Angeles Branch (UCLA MLIS Alumni)	

Amanda Meeks	Librarian, Northern Arizona University	This practice harms everyone involved and is especially unfair to those hired into temporary positions.
Summer Krstevska	Librarian, National University, San Diego, CA	The importance of librarians being valued and having the support of their institution is an ongoing battle. Supporting temporary contract goes against any progress we've made as librarians to be valued.
Carl Hess	Information Literacy Librarian Southeast Missouri State University	
Lisa Labovitch	History Specialist, Everett Public Library, Everett, WA	Not supporting full-time positions with benefits for library and archives professionals erodes our professions as a whole. Administrators with the power to add or remove positions will begin to see our labor as disposable, and our colleagues as interchangeable rather than possessing their own valuable skill sets and strengths. Eventually there will be a massive drain in talent as qualified professionals can no longer support themselves and pay off student loans with the term, part-time, and temporary positions that are on offer. Moreover, this kind of hiring practice works against efforts to increase diversity within the profession, making it only feasible for a narrow subset of candidates who can afford to work temporary or part time positions. Constantly having to hustle up new term positions is highly stressful, and takes a toll on productivity and professional morale; we lose a lot of talented people to burnout due to these practices.
Samantha Alfrey	Research and Instruction Librarian, Whittier College	
Nicollette Brant	UCLA MLIS Candidate, UCLA Library student employee (YRL)	
Brianna Toth	UCLA MLIS MAS Candidate 2019	
Alexis Recto	UCLA MLIS Candidate, Archival Studies 2019	
Raisha Pacella	UCLA MLIS Candidate 2019, Graduate School of Education & Information Science	
Dvorah (Deborah) Lewis	Genealogy & Local History Librarian, Sutro Library - California State Library, San Francisco	As an alumna of the MLIS program and a former employee, I support this completely. I know firsthand how stressful it is to jump from one temporary job to the next. UCLA should set an example and inspire other institutions to follow suit, especially since UCLA is home to such a great MLIS program.

Ana D. Rodriguez	South Florida Librarian, Florida International University, Miami, FL	Wholeheartedly support the UCLA archivists. I am also working on a temporary basis, and know firsthand the struggle of securing a position, period, in this field. UCLA and other libraries too need to get their act together, to bring job security, stability, and professional recognition to the archival profession
Rick Prelinger	Professor, Film & Digital Media, UC Santa Cruz	Equity, institutional memory, quality of services and the dignity of archival labor are all intertwined.
Andrea Leigh	Supervisory Librarian, Library of Congress Packard Campus for Audio Visual Conservation (not an endorsement/statement/approval from my workplace); former Library Assistant and Associate Librarian at UCLA; MLIS, B.A., UCLA	UCLA LSC should be ashamed that it is unfairly compensating full time archivists. Doing so devalues the profession and places valuable collections at risk.
Isaac Williams	Digital Library Program, UCLA MLIS (informatics) student	With all the work archivists do at LSC, it's only fair that they are given economic and job security.
Yuri Shimoda	UCLA MLIS (Media Archival Studies) Candidate 2019, UCLA Library Graduate Student Assistant (Music Library and formerly Library Special Collections)	
Annie Tang	Processing Archivist, Johns Hopkins University; former UCLA CFPRT intern and ARL/SAA Mosaic Fellow at UCLA Library Special Collections (LSC)	An institution as world-class as UCLA should do better by its employees! Particularly with such a busy Special Collections reading room as UCLA's. It is shameful most of the archives staff is temporary. It should be the reverse, as is the trend among many libraries, which only have 1 or 2 archists per repository. Most archivists of a Special Collections department should be part of the permanent line budget. This is so displeasing and disappointing to hear about my former workplace and alma mater.
Peggy Davis	Continuing Lecturer, UCLA Writing Programs	
Julie Botnick	UCLA MLIS Archives Candidate 2019	
Joy Rowe	Former academic archivist, Simon Fraser University	New professionals can be in temporary archivist academic positions for 5 years. How is that temporary work? oThis is a systemic problem that needs to be resisted everywhere.
Claire LaPolt	Librarian, Flintridge Preparatory School ; UCLA MLIS 2014	
Emily Drabinski	Librarian, Long Island University, Brooklyn; President, Long Island	Working conditions are teaching, learning, and researching conditions. Do right by these

	University Faculty Federation	workers!
Liz Cheney	UCLA Science Libraries	
Ali Versluis	Open Educational Resources Librarian, University of Guelph	
Brian Rogers	Librarian, University of Tennessee at Chattanooga	
Elizabeth Randell Upton	UCLA, HASoM, Musicology	
Glenda Goodman	University of Pennsylvania, Music	
Roger Gillis	Copyright & Digital Humanities Librarian, Dalhousie University	
Amanda Demeter	Assistant Archivist, King County Archives	
Abby Flanigan	Research Librarian for Music and Performing Arts, University of Virginia	
Jiaying Guo	Simmons College MLIS Candidate, 2019	
Katie Wilson	Biosciences Librarian and Data Curator, University of Minnesota	
Steve Duckworth	University Archivist, Oregon Health & Science University	
Alessandra Seiter	Simmons College MLIS Candidate '19	
Maria Aghazarian	E-Resources and Scholarly Communications Specialist, Swarthmore College	
Julia Stein	Archivist, Independent	
Patricia Hswe	Program Officer for Scholarly Communications, Mellon Foundation	
Bonnie Gordon	Digital Archivist, Rockefeller Archive Center	
Michael Pazmino	UCLA Film & Television Archive	
Matt Francis	Archivist, Ohio Northern University	
Amy Sloper	Film Archivist, Wisconsin Center for Film & Theater Research / UCLA MIAS '06 / former UCLA YRL staffSe	

Lauren Algee	Senior Innovation Specialist, LC Labs, Library of Congress (this in no way is an endorsement/approval/official statement from my workplace)	
Saida Largaespada	UCLA MLIS Graduate, Musician Estate Archivist	As someone who received both her BA and MLIS from UCLA, I made the decision to not apply to work within academia as an archivist because of contingent labor practices and the financial and healthcare impact uncertainty of employment would have on my family.
Krystell Jimenez	UCLA MLIS Candidate 2019	
Zayda Delgado	Librarian, Sonoma County Library	
Bethany Anderson	Archival Operations and Reference Specialist, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	
Tiffany Ito	University of Colorado Boulder UCLA '89	
Mary Wegmann	Collection Development Librarian, SSU	
Mitchell C. Brown	Librarian, University of California irvine, Scholarly Communications Coordinator	
Caroline Gil Rodriguez	Fellow in Media Conservation, MoMA	
Carol Lubkowski	Music Librarian, Wellesley College	
Kristen LaBonte	Associate Librarian, UC Santa Barbara	
Axel E Borg	Food and Wine Science Bibliographer, Shields Library, UCD	
Lane Goldszer	Librarian, San Francisco Public Library, James C. Hormel LGBTQIA Center	As a UCLA MLIS alumnus, I wholeheartedly support the positions expressed in the letter above. Temporary hiring practiced on a long term basis is harmful to all.
Ellen H. Belcher	Special Collections Librarian, Lloyd Sealy Library, John Jay College of Criminal Justice/CUNY	Temporary archivist/librarian positions are damaging to the collections, patrons, students, faculty, library and staff. They are a false economy. If the institution commits to collecting, caring for and making collections available, it should also commit to the professional staff needed to make that happen - permanently.
Gina Schlesselman-Tarango	Associate Librarian, California State	

	University San Bernardino	
Elizabeth Meyers	UCLA MLIS '19 candidate	
Stacie Williams	Digital Scholarship team Lead, Case Western Reserve University	Temp positions devalue the field, our work and our collections. They perpetuate deep inequalities between groups of people in our profession. Period.
Quentin Pace	UNT MSLS '18 candidate	
Josue Hurtado	Coordinator of Public Services and Outreach. Special Collections Research Center. Temple University	
Jessica Geiser	UCLA MLIS Alum; Collections Management Librarian, UC Riverside	
Supriya Wronkiewicz	San Francisco Ballet Archivist, Museum of Performance + Design, San Francisco, CA	
Sarah Mae Harper	UCLA MLIS Alum; former UCLA Library student employee (YRL); Librarian, LA County Library	
Yvonne Ng	Senior Archivist, WITNESS	
Adam Foster	UCL,A, MLIS / MAS 2019 Candidate, IS Lab Assistant III	
Ryder Kouba	Digital Collections Archivist; American University in Cairo	
Emily Vickers	Music Librarian, Eastern Washington University	
Becca Bender	Audiovisual Archivist	
Elizabeth M. Caringola	Archival Metadata Librarian, University of Maryland, College Park	
Christina Hicks	Youth Service Librarian, Friendswood Public Library	
Emily Lofquist	Youth Librarian, Kent District Library	
Gavin Strassel	UAW Archivist, Wayne State University	Solidarity forever
Adam Burke	Librarian, Waubensee Community College	

Erin Faulder	Digital Archivist, Cornell University	Relying on temporary labor is not a solution to overcommitted services. This practice hides the valuable contribution our professionals make by claiming the work could be “finished” at any given time.
Rita Johnston	Digital Production Librarian, UNC Charlotte	
Jolene M. Beiser	Project Archivist, Cornell University Library	I am a former temporary UCLA LSC worker. Not investing in employees and their careers is unfair and exploitative, and sets a terrible example for similar institutions and the profession at large.
Matthew Snyder	Archivist, Special Collections, The New York Public Library	
Jess Whyte	Digital Preservation and Intake Coordinator, University of Toronto Libraries	
Weatherly Stephan	Head of Archival Collections Management, New York University	
Julia Kim	Digital Assets Specialist, American Folklife Center (Library of Congress, but this in no way is an endorsement/approval/official statement from my workplace)	
Joanna Gadsby	Instruction Coordinator & Reference Librarian, UMBC	
Jim DelRosso	Associate Librarian, Digital Projects Coordinator, Cornell University	
Sherry Lochhaas	E-Resource Specialist, UC Berkeley	
Cathy Aster	Digital Library Product & Service Manager, Stanford University Libraries	
Shae Rafferty	Labor and Urban Affairs Collections Archivist, Wayne State University	
Teague Schneider	Sr. Manager of Oral History Projects, Academy of Motion Picture Arts & Sciences Foundation (not an official endorsement from the Academy, just from me)	I believe in Archivists and Librarians’ workplace rights and for temporary workers it is even more difficult to make an adequate salary for what is highly skilled technical and cultural work.
Sofia Becerra-Licha	Associate Director, Berklee Archives	
Nicole McKeon	UCLA MLIS Graduate; Go For Broke National Education Center	

Sara A. Howard	Librarian for Gender & Sexuality Studies, Princeton University	
Harry Eskin	Processing Archivist, Multicom Entertainment Group, Los Angeles, CA	
Eamon Tewell	Reference and Instruction Librarian, Long Island University	Hiring archivists on temporary contracts is harmful to the workers and users, and ultimately the university and collections. Create continuing appointments for the people who work hard for their institution and open up access to knowledge.
Tressa Graves	AV Assessment & Process Assistant, The Ohio State University	
Rachel Jaffe	Metadata Librarian, UC Santa Cruz	
Heather Hughes	Librarian, UC Santa Barbara	
Dale J. Correa	Librarian, UT Austin	
Carolyn Caffrey Gardner	Information Literacy Coordinator, CSU Dominguez Hills	
Dorothea Salo	Faculty Associate, Information School, University of Wisconsin-Madison	I cannot ethically suggest that my students and graduates pursue employment with you under these circumstances; therefore I will not -- in fact, I will actively warn them away from you.
Jacob Berg	Senior Librarian, The LAC Group	Please create continuing appointments for archivists and other information professionals. Do right by your staff and remove their precarity.
Kathleen DeLaurenti	Head Librarian, Freidheim Library, The Peabody Institute of the Johns Hopkins University	
Lauren Goodley	Archivist, The Wittliff Collections, Texas State University	
Emily Sommers	Digital Records Archivist, University of Toronto Archives & Records Management Services, University of Toronto Libraries	
Siobhan Hagan	Memory Lab Network Project Manager, DC Public Library; former AV Preservation Specialist at UCLA Library	My time at UCLA Library was majorly influential to my life and career, and I am confident that this esteemed institution can pave the way for our profession in creating continuing appointments and a transparent and sustainable pathway for temporary positions to become permanent.
Emily Sulzer	MLIS student, UCLA	

	Project archivist, Center for the Study of Political Graphics	
Joanna Smith	UCLA MLIS Student, and Center for Primary Research and Training Digital Archive Program Scholar at UCLA	
Alexa Logush	MA/MLIS, New York University	
Lydia Willoughby	Research and Education Librarian, State University of New York at New Paltz	
Sam Meister	Preservation Communities Manager, Educopia Institute	
Jeanette Duffels	Director of Knowledge and Information Management, Southern California University of Health Sciences	
Nicole Meyer	UCLA MLIS Student, and Center for Primary Research and Training Digital Archive Program Scholar at UCLA	
Peggy Griesinger	Metadata Librarian, George Mason University Libraries	
Theresa Berger	California Revealed	
Patrick Queen	UCLA MLIS Student, and CFPRT Scholar in Library Special Collections	I have seen this sort of modular thinking in corporate sector jobs. It is dehumanizing, demoralizing, and inefficient, and therefore, has no place in the archival profession.
Kim Edwards	Information Analyst for Technical Services, George Mason University Libraries	
Kelsey O'Connell	Digital Archivist, Northwestern University Libraries	
Genna Duplisea	Archivist and Special Collections Librarian, Salve Regina University	
Mary-Michelle Moore	Reference & Instruction Librarian, Librarian for Communication UC Santa Barbara	
Kirsten Ismene Schilling	California Revealed	
Aliqae Geraci	Assistant Director, Catherwood Research and Learning Services, Cornell University	

Tom Philo	Archivist/Cataloger, CSU Dominguez Hills	
Tim DiLauro	Data Archivist, Johns Hopkins University	
Mary Leverance	Preservation Coordinator, University of Arkansas	
Gr Keer	Associate Librarian, Online Learning & Outreach, Cal State East Bay	
Diane Gurman	Librarian, LAPL; former UCLA Scholarly Communication and Licensing Librarian	
Maggie Schreiner	Archivist, Brooklyn Historical Society	Signing in solidarity with all workers in term positions! And thanking you for laying out the many problems with temporary positions in our field in such a thorough and powerful way!
Heather Fox	Manuscripts Archivist/Director, Oral History Center, University of Louisville	
Graeme Slaght	Scholarly Communications & Copyright Outreach Librarian, University of Toronto Libraries	
Emily Yen	UCLA, Sociology	
Sara Bond	UCLA MLIS '18; Librarian at Jet Propulsion Laboratory; former student employee at UCLA Science and Engineering Library and UCLA Biomed Library	
Jessica Farrell	Curator of Digital Collections, Harvard Law School Library Historical & Special Collections	This letter outlines well both the ethical and operational pitfalls of contingent labor. This is a trend that has reached a critical point and if we want both our profession and our archives to survive, it has to change.
Rebecca Hirsch	Yale University Libraries	
Gayle Schechter	Digital Exhibitions Coordinator, Atlanta University Center Robert W. Woodruff Library	
Kelly Davis	MSLIS (Pratt Institute, 2014); Getty Research Institute	Temporary, contract positions force information professionals to sacrifice stability to work in their field. Permanent positions are not only better for the employee, they are better for the institution.
Katie Duvall	Archivist, National Anthropological Archives, Smithsonian Institution;	

	UCLA MLIS alum	
Brian Block	UCLA MLIS alum; former CFPRT Scholar at UCLA LSC	
Matthew Farrell	Digital Records Archivist, Duke University Archives	
Jessica Gambling	UCLA MLIS, 2007; Archivist, Los Angeles County Museum of Art	
Taylor Greene	Chapman University, Performing Arts Librarian/Coordinator of Reference Services	
Leigh Phan	UCLA Library Data Archive, Sustainable LA Grand Challenge	
Rand Boyd	Special Collections and Archive Librarian, Chapman University	
Wallace Meek	UCLA Film and Television Archive.	
Linta Kunnathuparambil	Library Assistant at Getty Research Institute	
Penny Coppernoll-Blach	UC San Diego Library, Biomedical Reference Librarian	
Wendolyn Vermeer	Collection Services Coordinator, CSU Dominguez Hills	
Richard Fraser	Independent Archivist	A long overdue reform.
Kelle Anzalone	MIAS Class of 2014	As a former temp archivist at UCSD I agree. This is a practice that strongly affects young archivists job outlook and sense of self worth. Institutions such as UCLA really need to consider investing in there employees by making them full time and permanent.
Anna Duer	Research Associate, Getty Conservation Institute; As-Needed Librarian, LAPL; UCLA IS Alum	
Karen Karyadi	Curatorial Assistant, Getty Museum; UCLA MLIS alum	
Sae Hee "Keshy" Jeong	Cataloging Assistant (former), California Institute of the Arts Film/Video and Image Services Library and Archives	
Megan Catalano	Curatorial Assistant, Getty Museum	
Frida Caro	Organizer, California/American Federation of Teachers	Librarians are a gift to our culture and society and they deserve the dignity and respect that

		their wisdom merits.
Annette Buckley	Research Librarian for Business, UC Irvine	I wholly support this.
Patricia Delara	Assistant Archivist, GLBT Historical Society	
Nicole Helregel	Research Librarian for Science Teaching & Learning, UC Irvine	I support this wholeheartedly. These professionals deserve respect, job security, and to have their work properly valued.
Jennifer Brown	Design & Technologies Librarian, Barnard College	This seems like a blatant, ongoing attempt at taking advantage of temporary employees, and an egregious devaluation of professionals in the field.
Melissa Gill	Metadata Specialist, Getty Research Institute; UCLA GSEIS Lecturer	
Evangeline Heath	Concerned Citizen	I agree with the above comment of Jennifer Brown. C'mon, we need you to be the good guys in a world that is going increasingly to the bad guys (and gals and all those in between) "This seems like a blatant, ongoing attempt at taking advantage of temporary employees, and an egregious devaluation of professionals in the field. "
Azatuhi Babayan	UCLA MLIS alum	
Cheryl Cordingley	UCLA MLIS Student, and CFPRT Digital Archive Program Scholar at UCLA	
Laura Uglean Jackson	Archives and Special Collections Librarian, Univ of Northern Colorado	
Judy Chou	Asset Curation Specialist, Walt Disney Studios	
Jonathan Farbowitz	Fellow in the Conservation of Computer-based Art, Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum	
Maggie Hoffman	Archivist, Cambridge Historical Society	The proliferation of temporary positions threatens both the continued professionalization of our field and the much-needed retention of institutional memory. Support your workers or you'll see your repositories' standards diminish.
Emmabeth Nanol	Metadata Assistant, Special Collections, Getty Research	

	Institute	
Uyen Hoang	UCLA Alum; MA in Asian American Studies MPH in Community Health Sciences	
Peter Musser	MLIS Student, University of British Columbia	As a resident and native of California living abroad, as much as I would like to return to my home state on graduation and work in libraries, work precarity like this is why I have to consider non-library jobs in and out of state. UCLA taking the lead on this could be the start of something important for us new folks, not just in California but across the country and perhaps North America.
Anya Montiel	Assistant Professor, University of Arizona	
Margot Note	Principal, Margot Note Consulting LLC; adjunct faculty, Sarah Lawrence College	
Mary Kidd	Systems & Operations Coordinator, New York Public Library	
Rachel Appel	Digital Projects & Services Librarian, Temple University	
Megan McShea	Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution	I am disturbed by the trend in my profession of increased reliance on contract labor for carrying out the core functions of our work. Archival institutions must consider the impact of precarious employment on the people they rely on to maintain the archives, and the impact on permanent staff of dealing with the continually shifting staffing. The cost of these ostensibly cost-saving practices is extremely high.
Meghan Courtney	Outreach Archivist, Walter P. Reuther Library, Archives of Labor and Urban Affairs, Wayne State University	The archival profession pays constant lip service to matters of diversity, but creates a system of unrealistic internships and short-term positions so only those with outside support are able to establish a career. Archivists' role in shaping the historic record is too important to leave up to money-minded middle managers who get a bonus for saving on benefits.
Samantha Smith	Project Archivist, Newberry Library	
Christine S. Engels	Archives Manager, Cincinnati Museum Center	
Laurie Duke	Head of Finance and Administration, Grey Art Gallery, New York University	

Shana Higgins	Librarian, University of Redlands	
Jessica Pierucci	Research Law Librarian, UC Irvine School of Law	
Rachel Searcy	Accessioning Archivist, New York University	Solidarity 🌹
Ellen Augustiniak	Law Librarian, UC Irvine	
Rayna Andrews	Archivist, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution	
Linda Murphy	Research Librarian for the Health Sciences, UC Irvine	
Jimmy Zavala	UC Irvine Special Collections and Archives Department	In solidarity with all temporary librarians.
Nicole Carpenter	Research Librarian for Social Sciences, UC Irvine	
Christina McClendon	Library and Technology Department Chair, Harvard-Westlake; UCLA MLIS	
Shahed Dowlatshahi	Media Preservation Specialist, New York University Libraries	
Jaya Dubey	Lecturer, Composition Program; UC Irvine	
Katherine Kapsidelis	Reference and Instruction Librarian, Special Collections, University of Southern California	The practices described in this letter are exploitative and greatly contribute to the devaluation of our profession.
Rachael Cristine Woody	Rachael Cristine Consulting	The use of temporary staff is inhumane, costly, irresponsible, threatens the collection, puts the institution at legal risk, and is generally untenable for all involved. I applaud UCLA's temporary staff and the UCLA colleagues supporting them, for taking a risky stand for the value of work they provide. Stop the devaluation of the profession, and UCLA: stop the devaluation of your colleagues, collection, and institution. You need to do BETTER.
Helen Kim	Institutional Archivist, Getty Research Institute	
Daniel Jessie	Lecturer, Department of Mathematics, UC Irvine	
Stephanie Revy Kaczkiwicz	Assistant Upper School Librarian, the Buckley School; former UCLA MLIS student	I entered this field, and was awarded the degree, with the understanding that I was joining the ranks of credentialed professionals. I consider my degree to be as professional as my

		brother's MBA from Anderson, or my sister-in-Law's JD from UCLA Law. However, the practices of this field devalue the professionalisation we have all worked hard to achieve. It is unthinkable to have "temporary" lawyers, or "temporary" quants and credit analysts; why, then, should it be acceptable to have "temporary" archivists performing non-temporary duties? UCLA, with its several professional schools, should be leading the charge in creating equitable employment environments for the fields it supports academically. The work of archivists is particularly vital in a research university (especially one that educates and creates new archivists). It is high time that their value is reflected through fair and reasonable employment practices.
Julian Smith-Newman	Lecturer in Composition, UCI	
Kristen Carter	UX Designer, Getty Trust	
Alexandra Solodkaya	UCLA Arts Library; Current UCLA MLIS Student	
Brian Dietz	Digital Program Librarian, NCSU Libraries (views mine)	The support for this is overwhelming. I expect that administrators at UCLA will take note, and I hope that administrators elsewhere do so, too.
Erik Kongshaug	Lecturer in Composition and in History, UCI	
Ann Tartsinis	PhD Candidate, Stanford University	
Quillan Rosen Kaser	Gallery Manager, UOVO	
Lily Rubinstein	Historian, Calibre Systems	
Cathy Vimuttinan	Lecturer in Academic English, UCI	
Pamela Posz	Library and Information Technology Program Coordinator - Sacramento City College	
Brendan Haidinger	Doctoral Candidate, University of Delaware, Dept. of History	Archivists' roll as the "Gatekeepers" of information is of singular importance. In the course of my own research, I have found that knowledgeable and invested archivists are critical to a project's success. The continued devaluation of LSC employees' labor is not only unethical and embarrassing to UCLA, but it clearly fails to fulfill the mission of archives more generally.
Lily Tonucci	UCLA Student	I Heart Books!

Heidi Herr	Outreach & Humanities Librarian, Special Collections, The Johns Hopkins University	
Louis Knecht	MLIS Graduate Class of 2018, UCLA; Instruction and Reference Librarian, Humboldt State University Special Collections	How can you expect your archivists, librarians, and information professionals to build their expertise in a given work environment when their job security hangs in the balance? Such practices by UCLA must stop and taking action can be a prominent and leading example for a majority of these respective fields that have made temporary positions a job market norm.
Michelle Janowiecki	Metadata Technician at Johns Hopkins University	
Gloria Rom	Retired DIIT staff	We are not as interchangeable and easy to replace as you seem to believe.
Katheryn Lawson	University of Delaware student, MLIS graduate 2017 (U of Iowa)	
Charmaine Bonner	Visiting Archivist for African American Collections, Emory University	As a temporary term archivist who is also an early career archivist, I'm directly affected by this issue. I agree that it needs to be addressed across the profession. I am definitely alarmed by the uneven distribution of new permanent archivist positions versus term positions. I feel this has a negative impact on archivist morale and overall retention rates.
Amy Griffin	MA, Winterthur Program in American Material Culture, 2016	This practice essentially equates your special collections with a game of "operator."
Laura Morris	Director of Archives and Research, Joan Mitchell Foundation	
Carrie Glenn	Doctoral Candidate, University of Delaware, UCLA alumna	
Brigid Cohen	Assistant Professor of Music, New York University	
Anastasia Day	Hagley Scholar, Phd Candidate in History at the University of Delaware	The adjunctification of higher education's instructional labor force is horrific enough. Extending these practices of insecure and tenuous employment to other areas of university labor is unacceptable, immoral, and unethical.
Ben Garceau	Lecturer, UC Irvine	
Hannah Frost	Stanford University Libraries	It is time for a reset. We are responsible for finding a way to sustainably resource the work -- and the workers who do the work -- that directly supports core services in research

		libraries. The archives are mounting ...
Sarah Glover	UC Irvine Special Collections & Archives	
Kiersten Mounce	PhD Candidate in Art History at the University of Delaware	Holding your employees--be they adjunct teachers or temporary archivists and librarians--in unsecure positions is unacceptable; it not only hinders the professional and personal lives of employees but hurts the institution in the long and short terms. Do better.
Jane Kelly	Historical & Special Collections Assistant, Harvard Law School Library; MSLIS Candidate, iSchool at University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign	As an early career archivist and current graduate student, I am gravely concerned about the impact contingent labor practices has on our field. These practices not only create many personal and financial difficulties for temporary staff, but shut down opportunities for many individuals who simply cannot take the risk of pursuing these types of jobs. Core functions of archives and libraries should not be squeezed into temporary positions. It devalues the work we do and the people who do it.
Kimberly Sørensen	Specialist, Design, Phillips Auctioneers	
Erin Debenport	Associate Professor, Anthropology, UCLA	I can't do my job without the expert work of UCLA librarians. These unfair labor practices must stop.
Emily Park	Library Assistant; Getty Research Institute	
Vika Zafrin	Digital Scholarship Librarian, Boston University	Signing in solidarity with UCLA colleagues. Contingent labor practices damage our intersecting fields. It's time for UCLA to step up in support of its workers.
Kelly Hahn	Associate Director, FAS Donor Relations, Harvard University; former student and staff administrative assistant, UCLA Library Special Collections	These librarians and this department deserve the personal and institutional security that is undermined by this unfair practice of temporary hiring. As a UCLA alumna, a former staff member of the department, and a donor relations professional, I urge to you change this practice and safeguard this essential part of the UCLA Library system.
Clarissa Douglass	Academic Affairs Liaison, Soka Gakkai International Relations, Tokyo	
Yvonne Sone	Collections Administrator, Los Angeles County Museum of Art	
Alycia Sellie	Associate Librarian for Collections,	

	CUNY Graduate Center	
Marie Silva	Archivist & Manuscripts Librarian, California Historical Society	Temporary labor practices are harmful and demoralizing, compromise our values, and undermine diversity in the archival profession. How can anyone with dependents to support, health issues, etc., rely on these precarious appointments? Our dedicated, hard-working colleagues deserve better.
Aaron Preacher	Former Student Assistant and Library Assistant, UCLA Library Special Collections	These temporary hiring practices are exploitative and shameful. Treating professional archivists as if they are disposable is beneath the dignity of this institution.
Jo Dutilloy	Circulation Assistant, University of the Arts Greenfield Library	On behalf of archivists and librarians suffering under unfair temporary and part time hiring practices at UCLA and elsewhere. Skilled workers require not only adequate compensation but also care, stability, and opportunities for education.
Ariadne Rehbein	Missouri State Archives	Thank you for speaking up for the personnel at UCLA Library; it strengthens our profession to advocate for what is right for us as employees, for the stewardship of collections, and for people who have to grapple with the professional and personal challenges of temporary employment.
Courtney Jacobs	UCLA Libraries Special Collections	Relationships with faculty, donors, and other stakeholders are harmed through the rapid turnover and lack of employee empowerment endemic in temporary employment. I support a fully staffed department - we should invest in workers if we expect them to invest in us!
Meredith Reese	UCLA Alumna; Digital Asset Manager, Los Angeles Philharmonic	
Alex Regan	UCSB Library, Events & Exhibitions Librarian	
Julie Seigel	Outreach Librarian, Prince George's Community College	
Anastasia Chiu	Stony Brook University	Where the intention is to fulfill known operational needs that are long-term and key/crucial to the institution's strategy & mission, and which require substantial expertise, experience, and other hard-bought qualifications to do well, it is exploitative to hire on a term-limited basis.
Tyler Putman	University of Delaware, PhD Candidate	Sustainable employment is key to the quality of preservation, interpretation, and access of archival and other collections

Jaime Henderson	Archivist, California Historical Society	A move to address this problem at the university level will, hopefully, impact special collections libraries in all types of organizations.
Berit Hoff	Director of Exhibitions and Program, Center for Architecture	
Meredith Broadway	Business Information and Data Analysis Librarian, Vanderbilt University	
Catherine Winiarski	Adjunct lecturer, Long Beach City College and Cerritos College	
Molly Brown	Reference and Outreach Archivist, Northeastern University	
Alejandra Gaeta	Archivist, Center for the Study of Political Graphics	
Nicole Shibata	Archivist, JAB Art Enterprises; UCLA MLIS 2010	
Margo Padilla	Archival Solutions Manager, Metropolitan New York Library Council	
Jonathan Ballak	Digital Asset Cataloger, Los Angeles Philharmonic, UCLA MLIS	
Amelia Acker	Assistant Professor, School of Information, University of Texas at Austin	
Faith Charlton	Lead Processing Archivist, Manuscripts Division Collections, Princeton University Library	
Yoonha Hwang	UCLA MLIS Candidate 2019; UCLA Richard C. Rudolph East Asian Library Student Library Assistant	It is disappointing to learn of these practices by the UCLA Library Special Collections.
Catherine Brown	Inquiry Librarian, Lead, Exhibits & Programs, UCLA Powell Library - retired	This was a common practice in an earlier administration. While we obtained some fine librarians after the temporary appointees became permanent, it is not fair to the temps or the institution who keeps having to train new hires, all in the name of saving money by hiring at a lower assistant level.
Taylor Dwyer	UCLA MLIS 2018	
Mohamed Haian Abdirahman	Project Archivist, Mellon Foundation	
Benjamin Wollet	PhD Candidate, University of Delaware	

Aggi Raeder	Science and Engineering Library (retired)	
John Bondurant	Digital Archivist, Cushing Memorial Library and Archives, Texas A&M University	It is shameful and shortsighted for UCLA or any institution to support such hiring practices.
Jared Campbell	Metadata Librarian, UC Davis	
Susan Malsbury	Digital Archivist, NYPL	
Annie Ross	Monographs Metadata Specialist, UC San Diego Library; UCLA M.A. alum	
Stephanie Geller	UCLA MLIS Candidate, UCLA Library student employee (Preservation)	
Richard Wheeler	Lecturer, UCLA Department of Design Media Arts; MFA alum, UCLA Department of Design Media Arts	
Cody Hennesy	Instruction Librarian, UC Berkeley Libraries	
Jenny Yap	Librarian, Berkeley City College	
Imad Abuelgasim	Librarian, Catalog & Metadata Services, UC Berkeley	
Christina V. Fidler	Archivist, Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, UC Berkeley	
Carla Arbagey	Collection Strategist and Electronic Resources Librarian, UC Riverside	
Lillian Castillo-Speed	Librarian, Ethnic Studies Library, UC Berkeley	
Licia Maria Hurst	UCLS MLIS alumna; consulting archivist, Santa Monica History Museum	
Sue Tyson	Archivist I, CA State Archives and alum, Post-MLIS Archival Studies Certificate, UCLA	The practice of stringing people along on soft money is harmful on so many levels and must be stopped. Archivists and their work should be respected. The archives field should reverse course away from the adjunctification that has been so damaging to academia.
Kendra K. Levine	Librarian, Institute of Transportation Studies Library, UC Berkeley	
Debbie Jan	Optometry and Health Sciences Librarian, UC Berkeley	

Jessica Wagner Webster	Digital Initiatives Librarian, Baruch College, City University of NY	
Dana Longley	Assistant Director for Library Instruction, SUNY Empire State College	
Lise Snyder	Librarian Emerita, UCLA Library, 1980 - 2015	After working so incredibly hard during the last full contract negotiations to clarify the language regarding the use of temporary appointments, and having to file a grievance against UC for egregiously violating the librarians contract, it is extremely disheartening to see the UCLA Library resume its former practices. For all the reasons stated above, it is totally exploitative and absolutely wrong.
Raymond Reece	Library Assistant V, UCLA Wm Andrews Clark Memorial Library 1979-1983 Librarian, UCLA Arts Library 1983-1997	
Maureen Callahan	Archivist, Smith College	UCLA is currently fortunate to have extremely talented archivists. The institution will not be able to retain them or grow their capacities if it does not provide a fair and stable environment for them.
Jodi Berkowitz	Technical Services Archivist, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	
Caitlin Pollock	Digital Humanities Librarian, IUPUI	
Sarah Melton	Head of Digital Scholarship, Boston College	
Tobias Higbie	Professor, UCLA History Department	The outstanding staff in Special Collections deserves job security. This situation is part of the wider under-funding of the Library on our campus.
Geoff Scholl	Library Technology Developer, Villanova University	
Ellen LeClere	UW-Madison iSchool	
Joseph Koivisto	Systems Librarian, University of Maryland	Dedication to archival practice and scholarship should mean dedication to establishing and maintaining the institutional infrastructure that support it. This includes supporting the professional status and well-being of archival staff & faculty.
John Zarrillo	Senior Archivist, New York University	

Tom Brittnacher	Geospatial Data Curator, UC Santa Barbara	
Adrienne Pruitt	Collections Management Archivist, Tufts University	
Ean Henninger	Auxiliary Librarian, North Vancouver District and Richmond Public Libraries	As these archivists note, precarious labour inhibits community-building, reduces diversity and inclusion, and has negative effects on libraries, workers, and the people they serve. I support more stable employment relationships for them and all workers.
Jane Nichols	Oregon State University Libraries	In solidarity
Brandon Locke	Director, LEADR, Michigan State University	
Justin Joque	Visualization Librarian, University of Michigan	
Max Eckard	Asst. Archivist, University of Michigan	
Martha McTear	Special Research Collections Cataloger/Metadata Librarian, UC Santa Barbara	
Michelle Everidge Anderson	Director of Strategic Initiatives, Witte Museum, San Antonio; PhD Candidate, University of Delaware	The archivists and librarians at UCLA have lent their expertise to my dissertation research. I hate to think that I was a part of devaluing their labor. They deserve better.
Craig Lee	PhD candidate, University of Delaware	
Elizabeth Jones-Minsinger	University of Delaware Library, Special Collections, Processing and Accessioning Assistant	
Staci Steinberger	Associate Curator, Decorative Arts and Design, Los Angeles County Museum of Art	
Kimberly Forsythe Russell	Former Student Assistant, UCLA Special Collections	
Paige Sundstrom	Economics & Business Librarian, UC Santa Barbara	
Elisabeth Maselli	Editor, Rutgers University Press	
Angela Schad	Reference Archivist and Digital Archives Specialist, Hagley Museum and Library	
Becky Koch	Library Conservator, Illinois State	

	University	
Katie Bonanno Lowe	Museum Educator, Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County	
Whitney Ray	Records Management Analyst, State Archives of North Carolina	
Katherine Crowe	Curator of Special Collections and Archives, University of Denver	As someone who started in a project position that was term-limited and non-benefited but required an MLIS who is now a hiring manager 10 years in, I can attest to the impact of multiple contract positions in non project-based roles (as was the case with more than a few of my colleagues when I started) on institutional continuity, quality of work, and institutional culture/staff morale.
Michaela Ullmann	Exile Studies Librarian, USC Libraries, Special Collections	In solidarity
Mahnaz Ghaznavi	UCLA MLIS and IS Adjunct Faculty	
David Fernández-Barrial	Foreign-Language Librarian, National Library Service for the Blind and Physically Handicapped, Library of Congress	In solidarity with temporary archivists and librarians who contribute to the mission of their institutions but who are not afforded the rights that they deserve.
Matthew McKinley	Metadata Harvest Programmer, California Digital Library	
Timothy Ryan Mendenhall	Metadata Librarian, Columbia University	
Annalise Berdini	Digital Archivist, Princeton University	The work being done by the UCLA archivists, both permanent and temporary, is of the highest quality. As a former UC employee, I was able to work with some of these people on collaborative projects and to continually overturn the positions will cost the institution and the profession.
Luke Baker	Former Curatorial Assistant, The Museum of Modern Art, New York (Currently an Independent Design Researcher and Writer)	I offer my full support to the UCLA LSC employees in their ongoing effort to prevent exploitative and unjust labor practices enacted by the UC system. As a volunteer labor organizer with UAW Local 2110 (representing MoMA employees, including curators, librarians and archivists), I witnessed firsthand the deleterious effects (both financial and professional) experienced by employees in temporary or contract positions. Chronic financial and job insecurity harms these workers, and it harms the institution. Please do the right thing and end your dependence on exploitative short-term labor.

Susan L Wiesner	Digital Humanist in Residence, Special Collections in the Performing Arts, University of Maryland Libraries	I wholeheartedly agree with this statement and fully support the UCLA archivists. As a contract employee myself, the constant reminders of the end of contract term weigh heavily and wreak havoc on living arrangements, future career choices, and financial stability (the salary for a more seasoned archivist/librarian on contract is generally lower than incoming permanent librarians, regardless of experience). this does not provide healthy work environment.
Miriam Schulz	PhD Candidate, Yiddish Studies, Columbia University	
David Bliss	Digital Processing Archivist, LLILAS Benson Latin American Studies and Collections, University of Texas at Austin	I enthusiastically endorse the critique put forth by this letter. Working in a temporary capacity can feel highly limiting and anxiety-inducing, and it hurts the institutions that have hired us.
Jason Sylvestre	Rare Books Librarian, Special Collections, University of Miami	This statement resonates with me in so many ways. As someone who spent 8 years moving from contract to contract in 5 different states I know first hand how much of a negative impact temporary positions have on personal finances, mental health, and career prospects. Value your employees by providing them long term stability.
Robin Kear	Liaison Librarian, University of Pittsburgh	For all of the reasons listed above, we are struggling with the legacy of continuously renewed one-year visiting contracts in our University Library System, which includes librarians and archivists.
Tyler Stump	Accessioning Archivist, Pennsylvania State Archives	Temporary contracts are detrimental to archives and the communities we serve. Long term stability is good for everyone involved.
Katherine Madison	Contract Processing Archivist, National Anthropological Archives, Smithsonian Institution	
Kate Joranson	University of Pittsburgh	Thank you for sharing your struggles publicly. We need more dialogue on the issues surrounding temporary contract workers. We are dealing with here at Pitt as well.
Martin Klein	Scientist, Research Library, Los Alamos National Laboratory	
Ashley Taylor	Archivist, University of Pittsburgh	As someone who has spent the past 7 years employed under the terms of year-to-year contracts, I understand the uncertainty and professional and personal instability caused by this type of system. Thank you for this thoughtful and well-articulated document.

Nicole Belolan, PhD	Public Historian and museum professional	
Amanda Brent	Processing Coordinator, Special Collections Research Center, George Mason University Libraries	As a former contract archivist myself, I can attest to the uncertain, demoralizing nature of temporary archives and library positions. An institution cannot claim to care about its employees when it operates in this way. Thank you for this articulate, thoughtful letter that gives a voice to many in the archives profession who struggle with this unprofessional practice.
Holly Rose McGee (nee Larson)	Digital A/V Assistant, Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	I only got a permanent position after 7 years of contract archiving because of dumb luck. The practice of relying on contract archivists is exponentially harmful to the contractors (no opportunity for long-term financial planning, for instance), the collections (loss of institutional memory), and the profession (lower standards for work and ethics). It also devolves our profession into an assembly-line production facility, based on metrics and deliverables, when so much of our work is creative thought (not possible under a deadline), mindfulness, and problem-solving, none of which can be contained by "estimated work hours". Do right by your employees and the profession, and take this opportunity to be a leader in the field.
Brenton Grom	Director, George Read II House & Gardens; formerly Curator of Special Collections & Head of Library Academic Programs, Delaware Historical Society	
Jacob Zaborowski	Alumnus, NYU-MIAP, Graduate Intern, Getty Research Institute, Los Angeles, CA	As an emerging professional, I am all too familiar with the burdens of contract work, chiefly, what happens to the collection when I am gone, especially if I am the only one tasked with A/V work? Many institutions hire contract people without considering sustainability past the contract's end, or shift that contract employee's workload onto (already) overworked permanent staff. Contract work for short-term projects is one thing, but temporary employees in order to maintain commitments to long-term sustainability? That's plain irresponsible, and I support this letter calling these conditions out for what they are.
Madison Sullivan	Business Research and Instruction Librarian, University of Washington Libraries, Seattle, WA	
Luiza Wainer	Metadata Librarian, Princeton University	

John Polito	President, Audio Mechanics	
Chrissy Rissmeyer	Librarian, UC Santa Barbara	
Sarah Wade	Special Collections Archivist, Getty Research Institute	
James Cheng	Library Data Analyst, University of Nevada Las Vegas Libraries	
Adriana Casarez	University of Texas at Austin MSIS candidate, Graduate Intern at UT Libraries	
Kathryn Puerini	Audiovisual Archives Manager, PETA Foundation	
Nicole Marino	Digital Scholarship and Instruction Librarian, Salve Regina University	
Michael Demers	Digital Technologies Librarian, Hagley Museum and Library	
Kolina Koltai	PhD Candidate, University of Texas at Austin, School of Information	
Matthew Murray	Library Fellow, University of Nevada, Las Vegas Libraries	
Kate Orazem	University of Texas at Austin, MSIS/MA '19, part-time archival processing assistant	
Adena Brons	Librarian, Simon Fraser University	
Emily Pearson	Instructional and Research Services Librarian, Whitman College	
Roberto C. Delgadillo	Research Services Librarian, University of California, Davis	
Elaine A. Franco	Librarian, UC Davis	
Philip Leers	Hammer Museum	
David Michalski	Social and Cultural Studies Librarian, UC Davis	
Rosalie Hooper	Project Curatorial and Interpretation Assistant, Philadelphia Museum of Art	
Alison Brislin	University of Texas at Austin, School of Information, MSIS '20	
Blake Graham	Digital Archivist, University of Nebraska-Lincoln	

Nicole Santiago	Processing Archivist, Environmental Design Archives, UC Berkeley	
Ginny Barnes	University of Texas at Austin, MSIS '19, and Graduate Research Assistant at UT Libraries	
Karen Bean	Digitization specialist MOF Seattle	
Christie S. Peterson	Head of Technical Services for Special Collections, Smith College	Term positions are not a solution for long-term institutional needs, and, speaking from my own experience as a project archivist, place significant stress on the archivists and their families
Rhonda Super	MA, MLIS, Serials Specialist, UCLA	This needs to be the start of the conversation about the staff environment at the UCLA Library. Leaving vacancies unfilled or replacing them with temporary or student help creates backlogs, a demoralized workforce, a vacuum in expertise, and costly time to correct misprocessed materials. Ms. Rom is right, we are not interchangeable. Positions require skill sets that take time to develop. Staff expertise should be recognized, appreciated, and given a voice.
John O'Neill	Archivist, Neil Young Archives	
Kristin MacDonough	Conservation Fellow, The Art Institute of Chicago; Alum NYU-MIAP	This is an incredibly irresponsible and short-sighted practice in archives and many cultural institutions. It's always surprising how many resources (time, money, knowledge) go into hiring and rehiring temporary staff; especially when those resources can and should be directed towards hiring and maintaining qualified staff and providing professional development opportunities for the skills needed to responsibly steward a collection.
Tori Maches	UCLA MLIS alum	
Sean McDonnell	Lecturer, UC Davis	
Amanda Raab	Librarian, Ohio Wesleyan, formerly Rock and Roll Hall of Fame Library and Archives	
Marilyn Ferdinand	Editorial Director, DePaul University	I rely on our librarians for so many things. Knowing I have someone on staff every day who knows the collections, permissions needs, and how to help me with library-related technology I use is vital to my work.
Laura	UCLA MLIS student	
Ariel Hahn	UCLA MLIS Student, Student	

	Worker at UCLA Digital Library	
Joyce Wang	UCLA MLIS student	
Geno Sanchez	UCLA MLIS '16, UCLA Digital Library	
Erik Fausak	Health Sciences Librarian, UC Davis	
Amy Belotti	Digital Content Librarian, Regis University. Pratt Institute MLIS '15.	
Charles Mahoney	Assistant Professor, California State University, Long Beach	
Emilee Mathews	Art & Design Librarian, Ohio State	I used work in the UC system and had the benefit of union representation. I urge you to work with the union to better all of your employee's lives.
Shannon K. Supple	Curator of Rare Books, Smith College (MA, USA) — and former UCLA and UC Berkeley librarian; UCLA alumna x2	UCLA has an opportunity to lead in resetting the national standard by not hiring temporary professionals to do core work. I would love to see my alma mater lead this necessary change in professional practice and hiring.
Amye McCarther	Archivist, New Museum	Thank you for having the courage to speak out on this. Having been on both sides of the issue, I can attest that the practice of hiring temporary positions to fulfill core responsibilities is ultimately counterproductive. Adopting the mentality of the gig economy is corrosive to our field. Gaps in employment stemming from this practice particularly affect professionals in states that offer little to no social safety net, especially as regards health insurance. How can we expect to be accorded the respect our expertise deserves if the very universities responsible for our training are engaged in labor practices that place us at an economic and professional disadvantage?
April Rodriguez	Film Archivist, Academy of Motion Picture Arts & Sciences	
Jennifer "JJ" Harbster	Librarian, UC Davis	In solidarity
Elena Cordova	Processing Specialist, Rauner Special Collections Library, Dartmouth College	
Heather Smedberg	UC San Diego Library Special Collections & Archives	
Lee Riggs	Library Instruction, UC Davis	nb
Emily Deason	Researcher, filmmaker	Loyalty and service is a two way street. The

		failure of this institution to properly support the stewards of these precious and irreplaceable materials is a bad look, to say the least, and is a detriment to the psyche and morale of both the individuals and the institution as a whole.
Peter T. Johnson	Bibliographer, Princeton Univ. Libraries [retired]	Gig economy employment practices are counter-productive for the work described.
Rachel Van Unen	Archivist for Collections, MIT Libraries	
Stephanie Kays	Librarian, Denison University	
Joanna Black	Digital Archivist, Sierra Club	
Samuel Brandt	PhD Student, Department of Geography, UCLA	
Gregory Leazer	Assoc. Prof, UCLA Dept. of Information Studies	I see a role for both temporary project work in libraries and archives, and also for finding mechanisms for transitioning recent grads from their training programs into the profession. However, that logic can be abused, and maintaining a revolving door of professionals who contribute to both the missions of the library and university is unfair. Failure to commit to these individuals, and the profession they represent, contributes to the marginalization of librarians and archivists at UCLA and other academic institutions, and undermines the professional status of our field.
Maxwell Zupke	Library Special Collections Student Supervisor	
Dylan Flesch	Media Asset Librarian, KEXP	
Abby Adams	Digital Archivist, Harry Ransom Center, University of Texas at Austin	
Jessica McIntyre	Librarian/Archivist, Portland Art Museum	
Alexis Pavenick	Senior Assistant Librarian, California State University, Long Beach	
Emily Higgs	NCSU Libraries Fellow, North Carolina State University (views my own)	
Hilary Swett	Librarian/Archivist, Writers Guild Foundation	Kudos to the UCLA staff members for speaking up. I look forward to the profession-wide conversation that I hope will ensue.
Christine Cheng	Librarian, UC Davis	

Jessica Herrick	Archivist II, California State Archives	
Sheridan Sayles	Archivist, Rutgers University	Thanks for speaking out and I plan to help keep the conversation going.
Lisa Vallen	Archivist, UC Merced	
Anna Lacy	PhD Candidate, Department of History, University of Delaware	
Anne Connor	Los Angeles Public Library, retired	Recognition of the hard work of “temporary” staff is long overdue.
Jeff Rankin	Supervisor Reader Services, Department of Special Collections, UCLA (retired)	
Daisy Domínguez	Reference and Information Literacy Librarian, The City College of New York, CUNY	
Steven Ovadia	Professor/Deputy Chief Librarian, LaGuardia Community College, CUNY	
Jhensen Ortiz	Assistant Librarian, CUNY Dominican Studies Institute Library	
Leyla Cabugos	Librarian, UC Davis	
Kate Neptune	Processing Archivist, Harvard	The overuse of temporary positions is a scourge across our profession, and I commend the archivists of UCLA for speaking up so eloquently.
Bill Landis	Head of Public Services, Manuscripts and Archives, Yale University Library (views are my own, not my institution’s)	While there is a role for term professional positions to accomplish grant- or gift-funded projects, the abuse of these types of positions to accomplish routine work is a shot in the foot for UCLA’s library, students, and faculty. It also diminishes the library and archives profession writ large, and demeans the work of students graduating from one of the premier archives and library education graduate programs living right next door to the Young Research Library .
Ann Hubble	Librarian, UC Santa Cruz, UCLA MLIS alum	
Sarah Lindsey	Librarian, UC Santa Cruz	
Mary deVries	Project Archivist, (Temporary Librarian) UC Santa Cruz	
Christy Hightower	Librarian, UC Santa Cruz, and UCLA MLIS alum	
Kaley Jones	Graduate Student, University of	

	Texas School of Information; Archival Aide, Lyndon B. Johnson Library and Museum	
Jenny Swadosh	Associate Archivist, New School Libraries and Special Collections (and member of IBT Local 1205)	
Lydia Spotts	Archivist, Indianapolis Museum of Art at Newfields	Academic institutions produce archivists. Flagship universities need to demonstrate a commitment to our profession in hiring us for full time positions.
Adam Siegel	Librarian, UC Davis	The archives are the memory institution par excellence. The reliance on short-term disposable labor to maintain memory institutions over the long term is one of those perverse paradoxes only late capitalism can give us, and we should expect and must demand better from the "greatest public university system in the world."
Robert Farrell	Librarian, Lehman College, City University of New York	
Alex Jenkins	Reference Librarian, Newport Beach Public Library, CA	rose
Martin Gengenbach	Archivist, Gates Archive	
Karen Ranalletta	President, CUPE 2950 - Clerical, Library and Theatre Workers at the University of British Columbia Chair, CUPE BC Library Committee Co-Chair, CUPE National Library Workers Committee	
Jess Waggoner	Digital Initiatives Librarian, UC Santa Cruz	
Anna Robinson-Sweet	Assistant Archivist, The New School	
Deborah Costa	UCLA College Library, retired after working as a librarian from 1975 - 2011	
Chloe Noland	Assistant Librarian, American Jewish University	
Megan Prelinger	Prelinger Library, co-founder & information designer	End unfair temp labor practices now! Memory institutions betray their core purpose when they resort to labor practices borrowed from the gig economy! Build memory institutions by investing in archivists!

Amanda Burr	Mellon Fellow, Paper, LACMA Conservation Center	
Laura Schroffel	Digital Archivist, Getty Research Institute	
Brandon Burke	Archivist, Hoover Institution Library & Archives	
Molly Schwartz	Studio Manager, Metropolitan New York Library Council	
Carrie Hintz	Head of Collection Services, Rose Library, Emory University	
Liz Phillips	Archivist, UC Davis	
Amy C. Vo	Research Library and Archives Assistant, Monmouth County Historical Association	
Kylie Harris	UCLA MLIS alum, former CFPRT student employee Records manager	It is time UCLA sets an example in the field by converting these insecure, temporary archival positions into full-time, permanent positions.
Kim Hayden	Archivist, Center for Sacramento History	
Ellen Jarosz	Head of Special Collections and Archives, California State University, Northridge	
Azalea Camacho	University Library Archivist, California State University, Los Angeles	
Dylan McDonald	Archivist, Center for Sacramento History	
Al Bersch	Metadata and Systems Librarian, California Historical Society	
Michael Degerald	PhD Candidate, University of Washington	
Dana Gee	Project Cataloger, Haverhill Public Library	
Anna Trammell	University Archivist and Special Collections Librarian, Pacific Lutheran University, Tacoma, WA	
Marissa Friedman	Imaging Technician & Cataloger for Teaching California	
Lisa Zakharova	Archivist, Archives of the Big Bend, Sul Ross State University, TX	I signed on for four temporary project-based positions before I found my first permanent

		position, five years after graduation. It is almost a given that entry-level archivists have to do some temporary project work before they are able to find something permanent. Still, these are project positions using limited grant funds. To replace professional archivists with temporary archivists is against SAA Core Values and a shameful practice UCLA should be working to correct.
Sean P. Kilcoyne	Film Archivist, Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences	
Krystal Appiah	Instruction Librarian, University of Virginia and UCLA MLIS alum	
Jasmine Larkin	Assistant Project Archivist, New York University Libraries	
Erin Fussell	MLIS candidate, San Jose State University	
Julie Musson	Digital Collections Archivist, The Bancroft Library, UC Berkeley	
Tobias Higbie	Professor, UCLA History Department	
Karen Meyer-Roux	Archivist, Getty Research Institute	

Please add additional rows as needed